

HAL
open science

Membrane-based microfluidic systems for medical and biological applications

Silvia Tea Calzuola, Gwennyth Newman, Thomas Feaugas, Cécile M Perrault, Jean-Baptiste Blondé, Emmanuel Roy, Constance Porrini, Goran M Stojanovic, Jasmina Vidic

► **To cite this version:**

Silvia Tea Calzuola, Gwennyth Newman, Thomas Feaugas, Cécile M Perrault, Jean-Baptiste Blondé, et al.. Membrane-based microfluidic systems for medical and biological applications. *Lab on a Chip*, 2024, 24 (15), pp.3579-3603. 10.1039/d4lc00251b . hal-04732214

HAL Id: hal-04732214

<https://hal.science/hal-04732214v1>

Submitted on 11 Oct 2024

HAL is a multi-disciplinary open access archive for the deposit and dissemination of scientific research documents, whether they are published or not. The documents may come from teaching and research institutions in France or abroad, or from public or private research centers.

L'archive ouverte pluridisciplinaire **HAL**, est destinée au dépôt et à la diffusion de documents scientifiques de niveau recherche, publiés ou non, émanant des établissements d'enseignement et de recherche français ou étrangers, des laboratoires publics ou privés.

Membrane-based microfluidic systems for medical and biological applications

Received 00th January 20xx,
Accepted 00th January 20xx

DOI: 10.1039/x0xx00000x

Silvia Tea Calzuola^{a,b*}, Gwennyth Newman^{b,c}, Thomas Feugas^{b,c}, Cécile M. Perrault^b, Jean-Baptiste Blondé^b, Emmanuel Roy^b, Constance Porrini^b, Goran M. Stojanovic^d and Jasmina Vidic^e

Microfluidic devices with integrated membranes that enable control of mass transport in constrained environments have shown considerable growth over the last decade. Membranes are a key component in several industrial processes such as chemical, pharmaceutical, biotechnological, food, and metallurgy separation processes as well as waste management applications, allowing for modular and compact systems. Moreover, the miniaturization of a process through microfluidic devices leads to process intensification together with reagents, waste and cost reduction, and energy and space savings. The combination of membrane technology and microfluidic devices allows therefore magnification of their respective advantages, providing more valuable solutions not only for industrial processes but also for reproducing biological processes. This review focuses on membrane-based microfluidic devices for biomedical science with an emphasis on microfluidic artificial organs and organs-on-chip. We provide the basic concepts of membrane technology and the laws governing mass transport. The role of the membrane in biomedical microfluidic devices, along with the required properties, available materials, and current challenges are summarized. We believe that the present review may be a starting point and a resource for researchers who aim to replicate a biological phenomenon on-chip by applying membrane technology, for moving forward the biomedical applications.

1. Introduction

Microfluidics is a multidisciplinary field based on the manipulation of fluids within channels with dimensions on the order of tens to hundreds of micrometres. In such microchannels, the behaviour of a liquid is significantly different than at the macroscale due to the dominance of surface tension and viscosity, which allows precise prediction of the fluid flow¹.

In these constrained environments, reactions are highly dependent on mass transport, and the control of mass transport in microfluidic devices through membranes has grown considerably over the last decade². On the one hand, microfluidics allows the miniaturization of a process as well as the acceleration of reactions, reduction of reagents, waste and cost, and optimization of energy and space³. On the other hand, membranes are among the best technologies available in industrial waste management applications and filtration processes (e.g., biomedical⁴⁻⁵, pharmaceutical⁶, food⁶⁻⁷, and metallurgy processes), allowing for modular and compact systems. Therefore, the combination of microfluidics and membrane technology can magnify their respective advantages providing more valuable solutions not only for industrial processes but also for reproducing biological processes.

Microfluidics facilitates the recreation of biological processes by mimicking *in vivo* microenvironments into *in vitro* models as the organs-on-chip (OOC); but it can also facilitate tasks such as cell sorting⁸, DNA amplification⁹, and point-of-care diagnostics¹⁰ and detection^{11,12}.

In microfluidic devices for biomedical applications, membranes can play diverse roles including cell and particle separation, selective transport of biomolecules, and contribution to precise fluid control within the system. Furthermore, membranes can simulate physiological barriers, such as the intestinal, alveolar, or blood-brain barriers to study drug transport, disease mechanisms, and tissue interactions¹³⁻¹⁵ (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Schematic of the roles of membranes in microfluidic systems for biomedical application.

The choice of membrane materials is pivotal to the success of microfluidic devices. Materials like polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS), polyethylene glycol (PEG), and polycarbonate are commonly employed due to their biocompatibility, flexibility, and ease of fabrication¹⁶. These materials offer a range of physical properties suitable for different applications, allowing researchers to tailor membranes to specific experimental needs.

In summary, membranes in microfluidics play a crucial role in

^a UMR7646 Laboratoire d'hydrodynamique (LadHyX), Ecole Polytechnique, Palaiseau, France

^b Eden Tech, Paris, France

^c Department of Medicine and Surgery, Università degli Studi di Milano-Bicocca, Milan, Italy

^d Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, T. D. Obradovića 6, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

^e Micalis Institute, INRAE, AgroParisTech, Université Paris-Saclay, Jouy-en-Josas, France

* Correspondence: Silvia Tea Calzuola silviateacalzuola@gmail.com

replicating physiological barriers, facilitating cell interactions, and controlling molecular transport. Selecting appropriate membrane materials and properties is key to achieving the desired functionalities and advancing biomedical research applications.

This review aims to highlight the importance of the synergy between membrane technology and microfluidics to create more sophisticated and biologically relevant microfluidic platforms.

In this paper, the laws governing mass transport across membranes are introduced; then the current state and future perspectives of membrane technologies on organs-on-chip and microfluidic artificial organs are discussed. This work summarizes the roles of membranes in these devices, the required properties, the most suitable materials, and the current limitations to guide researchers in designing more effective membrane-based microfluidic devices.

2. Basics of membrane transport

A membrane is a selective barrier between two phases that allows mass transfer under the action of a driving force (e.g., gradients in pressure, temperature, concentration, or electrical potential)¹⁷. The stream that passes the membrane is called 'permeate', whereas the remainder is defined as 'retentate'. The transport mechanisms across a membrane depend on the membrane's morphology, and two typical morphologies can be distinguished: porous and dense.

In dense membranes, the interactions between permeate and membrane material dictate the transport rate and selectivity. Transport in such systems is described by the solution/diffusion model¹⁸ in which the combination of Fick's law (diffusion) and Henry's law (solubility) leads to the equation:

$$J = \frac{S_i * D_i * \Delta p}{\delta m} \quad (1)$$

where J is the flux of diffusing species normalized for the membrane surface area (mol/s m²), S_i is the solubility of the permeant i (mol/m³ Pa), D_i is the diffusion coefficient of the permeant in the material (m²/s), Δp is the pressure difference between the high and low-pressure side, and δm is the membrane thickness.

Two basic properties are used to evaluate the general performance of a dense membrane: permeability and selectivity. In the solution-diffusion model, the permeability P of component i is the product of a kinetic (D_i) and a thermodynamic term (S_i), and its value indicates the membrane transport capacity¹⁹.

$$P_i = S_i * D_i \quad (2)$$

Or from equation (1):

$$P_i = \frac{J_i * \delta m}{\Delta p} \quad (3)$$

The intrinsic selectivity α_{ij} , defined as the ratio of the pure permeabilities of components i and j , measures the membrane's ability to separate a desired component from the feed mixture²⁰

$$\alpha_{ij} = \frac{P_i}{P_j} = \frac{D_i}{D_j} \times \frac{S_i}{S_j} \quad (4)$$

Permeability of a membrane to a specific permeant is an intrinsic property of the membrane's material because both the solubility and diffusivity of component i depend on the chemical and physical interactions with the membrane's material. For example, in the case of gas separation through dense polymer membranes, D always decreases with the increasing size of the gas molecule. The extent of this decrease is generally dependent on the flexibility of the polymer backbone. On the other hand, the solubility of gases generally increases with molecular size, because the intermolecular forces between gas and polymer increase. These are some general rules which can be useful for a first understanding, while a comprehensive review of the relationships between material structure and transport properties can be found in the work of Matteucci *et al.*²¹ and Wang *et al.*²²

In porous membranes, transport occurs through the empty spaces in the membrane, as a consequence transport is governed in the first place by membrane morphology. Morphology includes surface and volume porosity, pore size distribution, and tortuosity. Depending on the pore size, different mechanisms will dominate molecular transport. These mechanisms include, broadly: Knudsen diffusion, surface diffusion, capillary condensation, and molecular sieving²³. For an exhaustive review of the permeation mechanisms in porous membranes, we like to refer to the work of Oyama *et al.*²⁴ and Stratis *et al.*²⁵

The properties used to estimate the separation performance of a porous membrane are permeance, retention, and molecular weight cut-off (MWCO). The permeance is defined as the net transport of constituents through the membrane². Since transport is not an intrinsic membrane material property, permeance is not normalized for the membrane thickness.

$$P_i = \frac{J_i}{\Delta p} \quad (5)$$

It is important to clearly distinguish the terms membrane permeance and permeability. The permeance represents the mass transfer performance of a porous membrane, while on the other hand, the permeability is an intrinsic characteristic of the dense material that composes the membrane. Thus, two PC membranes with different pore densities will have the same permeability for component i , but different permeances.

The selectivity of porous membranes is quantified by the Retention (R), a parameter related to the concentration of

component i in the feed and permeate as given by eqn. (6):

$$R_i = 1 - \left(c_{i,perm} / c_{i,feed} \right) \quad (6)$$

R is a dimensionless number; it varies between 0 (component i can pass through the membrane freely) to 1 (component i is completely retained). It depends on the ratio of molecular size to pore size, and it measures the efficiency of a filtration membrane²⁶.

A characteristic of a porous membrane that indicates whether separation will occur is the molecular weight cut-off (MWCO). The MWCO is defined as the molecular weight at which 90% of the feed is retained by the membrane and indicates the pore size.

In summary, the performance of dense membranes is strictly material-dependent, and it is evaluated by the membrane's permeability and selectivity. On the other hand, the performance of porous membranes is morphology and material-dependent and it is evaluated by parameters such as permeance, retention, and the MWCO. Membranes can be operated in two modes: in the so-called 'dead-end' mode, where a feed stream is completely transported through the membrane, or in continuous mode, in which the feed flows along the membrane. Similar to heat exchange, continuous operations can be performed in co-current, counter-current, and crossflow²⁷. Overall, the optimum performance in a membrane-based process comes from the optimization of the membrane module material and morphology as well as the optimization of process conditions.

3. Membrane-based Organs-on-Chip

Organs-on-chip (OOC) are microfluidic platforms that integrate human microtissues in a controlled microphysiological environment. OOC systems narrow the gap between *in vitro* and *in vivo* testing by recapitulating key aspects of human (patho)physiology as continuous perfusion of nutrients and mechanical stress, providing a promising tool for drug development and personalized medicine^{28–31}. Although each type of OOC is different, many of the OOC platforms developed so far consist of an 'organ' containing cells of the organ of interest and a perfusion compartment that can include blood vessel endothelial cells and/or immune cells.

Generally, a porous polymeric membrane is applied between the two compartments to provide structural support for cell layers and to ensure a separation of transport processes by confining convective fluid flow to the perfused channels while allowing for diffusive transport of nutrients, secreted factors, and metabolites between the compartments. Flexible membranes also enable the mechanical actuation and stretching of cells and have been used for emulating peristalsis-like motions in gut-on-chip or breathing in lung-on-chip. Similarly, non-porous membranes deflected by gas pressure

have been employed to compress or stretch cells in cartilage³², heart³³, and bone-on-chip³⁴ models.

It is known that cells react to environmental cues, thus all the physical properties of the membrane such as roughness^{35–40}, surface microstructure^{41–47}, mechanical strength^{48–58}, hydrophilicity^{35,36,52,59–62}, and porosity^{55,63–65} have a significant effect on cellular adhesion and membrane biocompatibility. Despite their importance, these aspects are often neglected in OOC in which membranes are typically obtained from commercial Transwell inserts^{66–75} or filter membranes^{76–84}.

In this chapter, we will discuss how membranes' physical properties affect cells, and we will describe the most employed membrane materials in organs on chip. We will then review the literature on the gut-on-chip as an example of membrane-based OOC. We believe that the gut-on-chip model presents the richest landscape for research due to its primary role in drug metabolism and microbiota-host cross-talk and its relevance in various infectious diseases.

For the sake of brevity, in this paper, we will not consider the other OOC models. For a detailed review of all membrane-based OOC, we would like to refer to the work of Rahimnejad *et al.*⁸⁵

3.1. Membrane properties

3.1.1 Surface roughness The surface roughness of the membrane can significantly influence cell behavior^{35–40}. Dowling *et al.*³⁵ altered polystyrene surface to determine the effect of surface roughness and plasma treatment on the adhesion and spreading of MG63 osteosarcoma cells. They observed an enhanced cell adhesion on substrates with higher surface roughness while, contrarily, roughness negatively affected the spreading of MG63, as spreading decreased as surface roughness increased. Similarly, Majhy *et al.*⁴⁰, who studied the cellular behaviour of cervical (HeLa) and breast (MDA MB 231) cancer cell lines on PDMS with a roughness ratio in the range of 1.05–3 (roughness:5–150 nm), explain that an intermediate roughness ratio (≈ 2) is optimal for the formation of focal adhesion points resulting in maximum cell–substrate interaction, stable adhesion, and therefore, the highest cell growth and proliferation. Above a critical roughness ratio, the cell membrane's elasticity precludes the cells' penetration into deep surface grooves, leading to only point-contact that reduces cell–substrate interaction and causes a notable drop in cell proliferation. Zhou *et al.*³⁹ demonstrated that the critical roughness level and thus the response to surface roughness stimulus is cell-type specific. They developed surface roughness gradients ranging from the nano to the micrometre scale on magnesium substrates to study the response of endothelial cells (ECs) and smooth muscle cells (SMCs) to improve the biocompatibility of vascular implants. Both cell types respond evidently to varying roughness on the Mg-based material, but high surface roughness (1.0–2.0 μm) with a network of ridge/valley structures provided a most favourable microenvironment to ECs proliferation while disfavoured that of SMCs.

3.1.2. Hydrophilicity Surface wettability is a measure of surface energy. Surface energy can be altered or tuned by the addition of hydrophobic or hydrophilic groups. Plasma treatment, for example, is a well-known procedure for increasing the hydrophilicity of many hydrophobic surfaces including PDMS, PET, PLGA, and COC. The hydrophilicity of a material is a strong determinant of protein adsorption and thus cell adhesion^{35,36,52,59,61,62,86}. In 2D cell culture, hydrophilic substrates promote cell adhesion and proliferation^{59,86}, with moderate hydrophilicity yielding often the best cell response^{61,62}. Conversely, in 3D cell culture, specifically for spheroid formation, high hydrophobic substrates induce the formation of spheroid-like cell aggregates at a higher degree of sphericity, as shown by Ferrari *et al.*⁶⁰ and Lee *et al.*⁸⁷ among others^{88–90}.

Zan *et al.*⁵² investigated the behaviors of three chondrogenic cell lines on PDMS substrates with different grades of hydrophilicity (WCA: 38.5°–120.4) and different stiffness (elastic modulus: 3.6–214.9 MPa). The response of different cell lines to an identical substrate was different, however, among the two factors influencing cell behaviours, the substrate wettability dominated cell proliferation while the substrate stiffness played a major role in the cell migration and spread and the expression of cell adhesive molecule and chondrogenic gene. This result confirms the suggestion of Wala *et al.*⁸⁶ that initial cell adhesion and proliferation are regulated by surface properties such as hydrophilicity and roughness, while material properties such as stiffness influence later stages of cell growth.

3.1.3. Mechanical stiffness Cells are not only sensitive to dynamic mechanical stimuli such as strain or fluidic shear stress but are also sensitive to the mechanical properties of the substrate such as the stiffness. The range of ECM stiffness in the body is massive. Many orders of magnitude separate the softest tissue - the brain, with an elastic modulus of tenths of kPa - to the hardest - calcified bones with a modulus of the hundreds of MPa - and each specific cell type is tuned to the mechanical environment in which it resides. In particular, the stiffness of the cell microenvironment has a crucial role in many physiological and pathological processes of blood vessels^{54,56,91–93} as well as in the differentiation fate of stem cells^{48,50,57,58}. Bosworth *et al.*⁵⁴ demonstrated that substrate stiffness influences the barrier function of the Blood-Brain barrier model. More specifically, iPSC-derived brain microvascular endothelial-like cells exhibit differences in passive but not in active barrier function in response to substrate stiffness. Recently, Zhou *et al.*⁵⁶ observed significant vascular cell differences while remaining in a physiological range of substrate stiffness (18 vs 86 kPa). Compared with the 18 kPa substrate, on the 86 kPa substrate, the size of VECs increased, the production of NO decreased, the proliferation rate increased, and cells showed 560 differentially expressed genes, indicating that even a small increase in stiffness within the physiological range have a higher impact on vascular cell behaviours.

Engler *et al.*⁴⁸ looked at the relationship between substrate stiffness and mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) differentiation, showing a dependency of the lineage of differentiation on the

stiffness of the substrate. Indeed, soft PAA substrates with a stiffness of 0.1–1 kPa corresponding to brain tissue and 8–17 kPa corresponding to muscles led to neurogenic and myogenic differentiation respectively, while stiff substrates of 25–40 kPa induced osteogenic differentiation.

3.1.4. Microstructures Many studies demonstrated the ability of cells to adapt their cytoskeleton and, if needed, the nucleus morphology as a response to the surface microtopographies^{41–47}. This ability is often exploited to align and guide the growth of nerve and muscle cells through substrate microstructures like wells or grooves. For instance, Peng *et al.*⁴⁷ proposed a micro/nanostructured PLGA conduit for nerve regeneration, which enhanced the migration rate and the cell guidance ability of immortalized neuron progenitors compared to flat PLGA membranes. Similar to microfibers or grooves, microchannels represent also a major category of microstructures and their geometry affects cellular behaviour, as demonstrated by Esch *et al.*⁴³. Esch and colleagues grew HUVECs on square and semi-circular microfluidic channels in static conditions and under flow, finding that the expression of VE-cadherin that regulates cell–cell interactions were similar in the two geometries. However, vinculin, responsible for focal adhesions, was less present in square channels than in semi-circular ones, suggesting that the latter promotes better cell–surface communication.

3.1.5. Porosity Porous membranes commonly used in tissue barrier and co-culture models allow the exchange of soluble factors between cell populations and in some cases even cell–cell physical contact⁶⁴. These membranes also provide mechanical support for the cells and establish a partition to define apical and basal compartments. Casillo *et al.*⁶³ grew endothelial cells on non-porous and porous SiO₂ membranes with different pore sizes and pore spacings. On porous membranes, cells showed fewer focal adhesions and less fibronectin fibrillogenesis than on nons with smaller pores compared to membranes with a bigger -porous substrate, and this effect was accentuated on membrane porosity. However, cell–cell interactions in the form of tight junctions measured by ZO-1 activity showed an opposite trend. They concluded that porosity, especially with small pore spacing, could limit cell adhesion, but weaker cell–substrate interaction might lead to stronger cell–cell interaction. Nonetheless, Wen *et al.*⁵⁸ found no influence of the porosity on the differentiation of ASCs on PAA hydrogels, suggesting that the effect of porosity on cells may depend on multiple factors.

Overall, chemical, and physical modifications of substrates and their effect on cell behavior are well studied and documented for cell culture on non-porous substrates, while yet limited research has been done on membrane-based models.

3.2. Membrane materials

Although a wide variety of natural and synthetic polymers is employed in the fabrication of scaffolds for tissue engineering, most OOC porous membranes are fabricated by only a few

polymers, namely: PDMS, PC, poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET), poly(1-caprolactone) (PCL) and Polylactic acid (PLA). Moreover, the choice of the membrane material is generally driven by practical reasons rather than the properties of the polymer related to the application.

The current repertoire of commercially available flat porous membranes is limited; mainly led by PC, and PET track-etched membranes produced for Transwell inserts or filter membranes. Their fabrication is based on irradiating the material to create tracks that are then etched to produce through pores with sizes ranging from 400 nm to 8 μm . The porosity of these membranes remains low to reduce the incidence of merged tracks or double pores, and the pores density is intrinsically nonuniform due to the random nature of the irradiation. Furthermore, these membranes are too thick and rigid to represent the native basal membrane.

PC track-etched membranes are extensively used in OoCs^{76–78,80,83,94–103} since reference data from PC Transwell cell culture are widely available, thus employing PC in OoCs seemed to be a natural way of transferring knowledge from the standard cell culture system. PC is a highly hydrophobic, inert, transparent, and non-biodegradable thermoplastic. It is very stiff, with Young's modulus of approximately 2–2.4 GPa which is not comparable to any body's tissues^{16,29}.

PET is another popular polymer for commercial membranes and inserts that is used in OoCs^{68,104–113}. PET shares many properties with PC; it is also a hydrophobic, inert, transparent thermoplastic with high stiffness (Young's modulus of 2–3 GPa)^{16,29,114}. Thus, like PC, PET is unsuitable for OoCs which apply stretch stimuli to the cells by deformation of the support membrane.

Among self-produced membranes, PDMS porous membranes are to date the most employed in OoCs^{115–123} since they join the advantages of PDMS to those of the fabrication methods. PDMS is a low-cost elastomeric polymer characterized by physiological indifference, biocompatibility, excellent resistance to biodegradation, chemical stability, excellent gas permeability, optical transparency, and a tuneable Young modulus in the physiological range (360 kPa – 2 MPa)^{124–126}. With its flexible nature and low elastic modulus, this polymer is the most suited for applying cyclic stretch to cells. Moreover, PDMS membranes are fabricated by commonly used microfabrication techniques such as spin coating and soft lithography, which allow control over pore size and pore-to-pore distance in the micrometre scale^{126,127}. Nevertheless, this polymer also features several drawbacks that are fuelling the demand for new alternative materials. PDMS is highly hydrophobic and requires surface modification approaches, as oxygen plasma, to improve its cell affinity^{128,129}. Besides, PDMS-based membranes absorb hydrophobic molecules such as drugs and markers commonly used in cell culture *in vitro* assays¹³⁰, compromising the study results. In addition, the fabrication techniques used for PDMS-based membranes and devices have limited scalability, thus hampering production at an industrially relevant scale¹³¹.

As an alternative to the before-mentioned biostable materials, biodegradable polymers like aliphatic polyesters such as PLA^{132–}

¹³⁵ and PCL^{136–141} are used to fabricate porous membranes for OoCs. PLA is one of the stiffest biocompatible polymers with Young's modulus of 3–4 GPa, making it unsuitable for membranes that should be exposed to mechanical stretch. It is, however, less hydrophobic compared to the polymers being investigated for OoCs (water contact angle of 61°)¹⁴². Contrarily, PCL is characterized by a lower Young modulus of 400 MPa and a glass transition temperature of -60°C¹²², resulting in a flexible polymer with a rubber-like consistency at room temperature. PCL is also one of the most hydrophobic polymers treated with a water contact angle of 140°¹⁴³. The biodegradable nature of both polymers holds the potential for functioning as a temporary membrane, to be later replaced by the ECM of the cells creating an entirely natural cell layer. Tough, it must be considered that the pores' size might change over time due to the degradation and that the acid degradation products could affect cells.

To overcome the limitations of synthetic polymer membranes, natural polymers have recently been adopted to produce membranes that better mimic the composition and function of the epithelial barrier. Arik *et al.*¹⁴⁴ described a viable new approach to construct vitrified membranes from collagen type I hydrogel, demonstrating improved biocompatibility and are subjected to biochemical degradation by collagenase II. Zamprognio *et al.*¹⁴⁵ developed two types of collagen/elastin membranes: vitrified and non-vitrified, with stiffnesses ranging from several hundred of kPa down to 1 kPa. Frenkel *et al.*¹⁴⁶ used a free-standing extracellular matrix gel to engineer a lymphatic vessel model. Furthermore, non-autologous proteins, such as spider silk proteins, have already been applied to form thick (3–9 μm) nonporous membranes to model the retinal pigment epithelium. Recently, Tasiopoulos *et al.*¹⁴⁷ synthesized 470 \pm 110 nm thin, mechanically robust, and fibrillar nanomembranes of recombinant spider silk proteins, where they grew endothelial and smooth muscle cells in the attempt to model the vessel wall.

3.3. Gut-on-Chip

The human intestine is a dynamic organ where intricate interactions between the host and microbes regulate intestinal balance. While various *in vitro* models of human intestinal diseases exist, many models struggle to reliably mimic human intestinal responses to biological changes and medical treatments (*Figure 2*).

Human colorectal adenocarcinoma lines such as the Caco-2 or HT-29 have been used as a source of human intestinal epithelial cells and they are often cultured in Transwell plates. These cell culture systems involve growing cells on a semi-permeable membrane that separates them into apical and basolateral compartments, providing the ability to measure cell barrier permeability and assess interactions between different cell types¹⁴⁸. Despite the versatile benefits of cell and tissue cultures, the static cultures of intestinal epithelial cells in the Transwell format are limited in replicating the *in vivo*-like 3D villous morphology. The absence of a 3D microenvironment is often a symptom of inadequate cytodifferentiation which may

High-throughput readouts

Physiological relevance

2D cell culture	Transwell culture	Organoids	Gut-on-chip
<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost effective • High-throughput screenings <p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low physiological relevance 	<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost effective • Cell co-culture • High-throughput screenings <p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2D culture • Static 	<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cellular complexity similar to native tissue <p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inaccessible lumen • Lack of microenvironmental factors (ECM, Stroma) 	<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High physiological relevance • When established, less labor intensive <p>Limitations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low-throughput screening • Costly

Figure 2: In vitro models. Overview of four in vitro models used to recapitulate the physiology and the disease phenotype of the gut. The main strengths and limitations of each model show the inverse relationship between physiological relevance and throughput.

result in inaccurate outcomes of these models¹⁴⁹.

Intestinal organoid models show promising cytodifferentiation and regeneration, but their inability to incorporate luminal flow and physical bowel movements hinders the accurate replication of complex host-microbe crosstalk¹⁴⁸.

Gut-on-chips, functioning as minimal tissue units, can replicate certain aspects of human physiology in both health and disease, providing insights into the underlying biology of diseases and tissue regeneration. Utilizing micro-scaled OOC, researchers can follow dynamic changes in cell and tissue functions via real-time monitoring through imaging techniques and sensors. OOCs also enable researchers to isolate and study the effects of single-cell type, cell-cell interactions, and tissue-tissue interactions, contributing to a deeper understanding of native organ function and the impacts of various treatments^{150–152} (Figure 3).

Different membranes' materials, coating, and functions employed in gut-on-chip devices are reported in Table 1. Its purpose is to give the reader a general idea of the occurrence of each membrane material and the respective choice of coating, as well as to summarise the different components of each Gut-on-Chip and the resulting main findings. Moreover, Table 1 reveals a notable emphasis on replicating physiological conditions in organ-on-chip technologies, particularly in terms of biological components and mechanical stimuli, but highlights slower progress in developing biomimetic porous membranes. Current limitations toward more physiologically relevant membrane models include excessive thickness, smooth surfaces with artificial pores that poorly replicate the native

basement membrane structure, and challenges in tuning membrane stiffness.

Biomembranes should be more extensively investigated as an intelligent biomimetic system to provide important stimuli to cells as well as enhance specific intercellular interactions within the OCC system. Finally, a key technological issue needs to be faced. The large-scale fabrication of microfluidic devices is challenging, and the integration of membranes is still laborious and time-consuming. Therefore, novel processing techniques of membranes in microfluidics are crucial for membrane-based microfluidics to reach its full potential.

Figure 3: Gut-on-chip. **A)** L. Wang proposed a gut-on-a-chip integrated with transepithelial electrical resistance (TEER) sensors and electrochemical sensors is proposed for dynamically simulating the formation of the physical intestinal barrier and monitoring the transport and absorption of Hg(II) in situ.²²⁹ **B)** C. S. Yong et al. recreated a physiodynamic mucosal interface-on-a-chip by growing patient-derived intestinal organoids epithelium under luminal flow and multi-axial stretching motions. They showed a successful co-culture of human fecal microbiome with the germ-free Caco-2 intestinal epithelium in their chip: An inset in the “Co-culture” shows the viability of the isolated human fecal microbiome acquired by confocal microscopy, while the maintenance of epithelial barrier function was assessed by normalizing TEER values.²³⁰ **C)** The microfluidic-based gut model from Jeon et al. allows the co-culture of human and microbial cells. The device has a gold-patterned microelectrode array that enables the impedance measure of the intestinal epithelial barrier cultured with Caco-2 cells and HUVECs²³¹. **A, B, and C** are licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

Table 1: Gut-on-chip in the literature

Reference	Chip & membrane material	Cell type	Flow rate	Mechanical strain	Microbiome/ bacteria co-culture	Main findings
A. Sontheimer Phelps <i>et al.</i> (2020)	PDMS; ECM-Coated PDMS porous membrane	Primary colonic epithelial cells	60 µL/h	No	No	Human colon-on-chip to recapitulate the formation of mucus bilayer . The chip provided an environment for goblet cell differentiation under conditions in which proliferative cells also remain present. The human colonic epithelial cells produced a mucus bilayer , containing an impenetrable and a penetrable mucus layer, with a total thickness of 500–600 µm
M. Nikolaev (2020)	PDMS; Hydrogel	human intestinal organoids	Static	No	No	Mini Gut: they induce intestinal stem cells to form tube-shaped epithelia with an accessible lumen and crypt- and villus-like domains. They include rare, specialized cell types; retain key physiological hallmarks of the intestine
A. Grassart, <i>et al.</i> (2019)	PDMS; ECM-Coated PDMS porous membrane	Caco-2, clone TC7	30 µL/h	10% in cell strain, 0.15 Hz in frequency	<i>Shigella flexneri</i>	Shigella infection : chip for interrogating the role of biophysical forces in host-pathogen interactions. <i>Shigella</i> infects enterocytes from the apical side, exploiting the crypt-like invaginations for early colonization, while intestinal peristalsis enhances invasion. It exploits intestine architecture and mechanical forces to maximize infectivity
H. J. Kim, <i>et al.</i> (2016)	PDMS; ECM-Coated PDMS porous membrane	Caco-2	30 µL/h	10% in cell strain, 0.15 Hz in frequency	VSL#3 Pharmaceutical Probiotic, Pathogenic bacteria (EIEC)	Mechanical stimulation+VSL#3 promote cell differentiation (villi formation) enhance intestinal barrier functions EIEC: Bacterial overgrowth, villi destruction. ↑ colonization in absence of mechanical deformation
C. M. Costello, <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Porous PLGA scaffolds with intestinal villus features	Caco-2	Static	No	<i>Salmonella typhimurium</i> , <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> , <i>Lactobacillus gasseri</i> , <i>Escherichia coli</i>	In this 3-D environment, probiotics exert their effects through different mechanisms. LAB was more effective at displaying pathogenic bacteria once it had colonized; Nissle was more effective at preventing attachment.
K. Y. Shim, <i>et al.</i> (2017)	PDMS; Collagen Villi scaffold	Caco-2	100 µL/min	No	No	The tridimensional topology of the gut tissue influence intestinal absorptive functionality
W. Shin <i>et al.</i> (2018)	PDMS; ECM-Coated PDMS porous membrane	Caco-2, PBMCS	50 µL/h	10% in cell strain, 0.15 Hz in frequency	VSL#3 Pharmaceutical Probiotic Pathogenic bacteria (EIEC)	VSL#3 after barrier dysfunction did not contribute to mitigating inflammatory reactions nor did it help to improve barrier function. VSL#3 treatment before the barrier dysfunction successfully suppressed the secretion of inflammatory cytokines
M. Kasendra, <i>et al.</i> (2018)	PDMS; ECM-Coated PDMS porous membrane	Human intestinal organoids	60 µL/h	10% in cell strain, 0.2 Hz in frequency	No	in vitro model of the duodenum portion of the human small intestine by combining microfluidic Organ Chip technology with organoid-based methods

L. Gijzen, <i>et al.</i> (2020)	PDMS, ECM-coated Collagen1 membrane	Caco-2, Goblet cells (HT29-MTX) Immune cells (THP-1, MUTZ-3)	2.02 $\mu\text{L}/\text{mL}$	No	No	3D biological modular multicellular perfused intestine-on-a-chip model able to mimic intestinal inflammation (addition of TNF-α and interleukin (IL)-1β)
R. Villenave, <i>et al.</i> (2017)	PDMS, PDMS porous membrane coated with Collagen1 + Matrigel	Caco-2, CVB1	30 $\mu\text{L}/\text{h}$	10% in cell strain, 0.15 Hz in frequency	No	<i>In vitro</i> analysis of human enterovirus infection, replication and infectious virus production.
S. Jalili-firoozinezhad <i>et al.</i> (2019)	PDMS	Caco-2, HIMECs, intestinal organoids	Aerobic 60 $\mu\text{L}/\text{h}$; Anerobic: N ₂ at 243 mL/min	10% in cell strain, 0.15 Hz in frequency	<i>B. Fragilis + Eubacterium, Oscillospira, Blautia, Sutterella, Biophila, Akkermansia, Ruminococcus, Bacteroides, Parabacteroides, Enterococcus and Citrobacter</i>	Control and real-time assessment of physiologically relevant oxygen gradients . The transmural hypoxia gradient increased intestinal barrier function and sustained a physiologically relevant level of microbial diversity (200 taxa from 11 genera)
S. Woojung <i>et al.</i> (2019)	PDMS; ECM-coated PDMS porous membrane	Caco-2	50 $\mu\text{L}/\text{h}$;	10% in cell strain, 0.15 Hz in frequency	<i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis and Eubacterium hallii</i>	The steady-state vertical oxygen gradient in the Chip does not compromise the viability, barrier function, mucin production, and the expression and localization of tight junction proteins. Two obligate anaerobic commensal gut microbiome were coculture without compromising cell viability
M. Chi <i>et al.</i> (2015)	PDMS; Fibronectin-coated Polyester porous membrane	Caco-2	0.1 to 10 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$	No	<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	Caco-2 cells cultured in the μFCCD at 0.5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 3 days reconstituted the mucus layer and formed villi and crypt-like structures . The numbers of both adherent and invaded bacterial cells per host cell were lower for μFCCD-cultured cells than transwell-cultured cells, indicating that the mucus layer acted as a physical barrier.
Y. Imura <i>et al.</i> (2009)	PDMS; Collagen1-coated Polyethylene porous membrane	Caco-2	1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$	No	No	Microbioassay system to evaluate the bioactivity of drugs . Reliable results; less consumption of cells and samples; shorter testing time.

ARTICLE							Journal Name
J. Yeon <i>et al.</i> (2009)	Analytical Chemistry	PDMS	Caco-2	20 $\mu\text{L}/\text{h}$	No	No	No need of cell culture on the chip, cells are trapped in microholes. No tight junctions formed. The trapped cells were viable after drug absorption; the permeability coefficient between human in vivo and P eff on the microfluidic device was significantly related.
H. Kamura <i>et al.</i> (2008)	Lab on Chip	PDMS Polyester porous membrane	Caco-2	10 - 100 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$	No	No	Microfluidic device with embedded stirrer-based micropumps and an optical fiber insert for on-line pharmacokinetic measurement
O. Henry <i>et al.</i> (2012)	Lab on Chip	gold electrodes on PC membrane	Caco-2, hAECs	60 $\mu\text{L}/\text{h}$	No	No	Microfluidic device with integrated electrodes for real-time TEER measurements on virtually any type of cell monolayer. Device tested on differentiated human airway epithelium and intestinal epithelium
N. Langerak <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology	PLA hollow capillary, 3D-printed chambers, glass cover slips	Caco-2	30, 60, 90, 125 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$	No	No	Inflow of $Q_0 = 125 \mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ gives a shear stress of the order of magnitude of the required physiological shear stress for the intestinal cells to differentiate (microvilli on the apical side and tight junction on the lateral side).
H. Kim <i>et al.</i> (2012)	Integrative Biology	PDMS, ECM-coated porous PDMS membrane	Caco-2	30 $\mu\text{L}/\text{h}$	10% in cell strain, 0.15 Hz in frequency	No	Caco-2 when exposed to continuous physiological mechanical cues (fluid flow, mech. deformations) undergo spontaneous villus morphogenesis and small intestine differentiation.

4. Membrane-based artificial organs

Membrane technology is the central component in many artificial organs (AO) including lungs, kidneys, liver, and pancreas. Although AO technology has improved significantly in the past few decades, the quality of life of patients with organ failure is still poor and the technology must be improved further. This chapter will summarize the state of the art of membrane technology for microfluidic membrane-based AO devices, with a focus on artificial lungs, along with the current challenges in this field.

4.1 Microfluidic Artificial Lungs

An artificial lung is a prosthetic device able to sustain the gas exchange performance of a normal functioning lung to assist an injured or recently transplanted lung or completely replace the native organ¹⁵³. Artificial lung technology can be split into short-term and long-term respiratory support.

Short-term supports include cardiopulmonary bypass system (CPB) that during open-heart bypass surgery takes over the pumping function of the heart and the gas exchange function of the lungs to maintain the body in its physiological state¹⁵⁴.

Long-term respiratory support is carried out through the extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO) system. This treatment is reserved for cases where mechanical ventilation cannot supply the necessary oxygen demand, i.e., in severe lung failure due to aging, chronic lung diseases, or acute virus infections (e.g. COVID-19, MERS)¹⁵⁵. The main purpose of the ECMO system is to provide support until the body naturally recovers (bridge-to-recovery)¹⁵⁶, or in rarer cases until the patient receives an organ transplant (bridge-to-transplantation)¹⁵⁷. ECMO is also used as a standard of care for premature neonates whose lungs are immature and cannot provide sufficient oxygenation to satisfy their physiological needs¹⁵⁸.

ECMO, however, has inherent complications such as bleeding due to erythrocyte and platelet damage, thrombosis due to contact activation of the coagulation cascade¹⁵⁹, arrhythmias, inflammation, and possible infections. It requires multiple transfusions to compensate for blood damage or to avoid hemodilution, especially for premature new-borns. As a result, most devices have clinical lifetimes measured in days and a systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS) occurs in 60% of ECMO survivors¹⁶⁰. Additional limitations include ECMO therapy being non-ambulatory, labour-intensive, time-limited, and costly.

A new class of miniaturized oxygenators based on microfluidic technology paves a promising avenue for the reduction of ECMO complications through the realization of portable biomimetic lung assist devices. Among the advantages of microfluidic oxygenators, we can cite^{161–163} :

1) Surface areas and priming volumes that are a fraction of current technologies thereby decreasing device size. The introduction of the dual-lumen cannula allowing for single-site cannulation coupled with more compact oxygenators could permit the awaking and early mobilization of ECMO patients, which has been shown to improve therapy outcomes and shorten hospitalization^{157,164,165}.

2) Blood flow networks are optimized to recreate branching angles, shear stresses, and pressures that recreate those experienced by blood in the lungs, thus improving biomimicry.

3) Hydraulic resistances within the physiological range, enabling the possibility to operate with natural pressures, eventually eliminating the need for blood pumps.

4) The possibility to operate with room air, eventually eliminating the need for gas cylinders and complications associated with hyperoxemia.

4.2 Membrane properties

In blood oxygenators, membranes are responsible for physically separating the blood side from the gas side while still allowing gas exchange. The requirements to be respected by membranes for ECMO systems are, firstly, to meet the desired gas permeability as well as a suitable selectivity for O₂/CO₂, and to maintain them over time. The ideal membrane should allow oxygen exchange rates comparable to the human lung, thus between 210–3200 ml/min¹⁶⁶. Secondly, mechanical, and chemical characteristics of the membrane should be stable and minimize or ideally avoid plasma leakage. Last but foremost, membrane materials should be hemocompatible, hence prevent protein adsorption, platelets activation, and inflammation. Hemocompatibility is so far the biggest challenge faced by membrane technology in AO.

To date, the main parameter characterizing ECMO membrane's performance is the oxygen and carbon dioxide transfer rate, N (mol/s), within the oxygenator. N is directly proportional to the mass transfer coefficient, K (mol/m² s Pa), to the gas exchange surface area A (m²), and to the driving force of gas exchange i.e., the difference in gas partial pressures:

$$N = K \Delta P A \quad (7)$$

N is also, by definition, inversely proportional to the total resistance to gas mass transport, R_{total} . As the membrane module can be described with a resistances-in-series model, R_{total} is related to the sum of the partial resistance in the gas, the membrane and the liquid phase, respectively^{154,166}

$$R_{total} = R_G + R_M + R_B \quad (8)$$

R_{total} can also be written in function of the mass transfer coefficient as:

$$R_{total} = \frac{1}{K_{total}} = \frac{1}{K_G} + \frac{1}{K_M} + \frac{1}{K_B} \quad (9)$$

When the diffusion coefficient in the membrane is constant and gas solubility in the polymer can be represented by a linear isotherm, Crank and Park (1968) expressed mass transfer resistance through the membrane as the ratio between the membrane thickness and its permeability:

$$\frac{1}{K_M} = \frac{\delta_M}{P} \quad (10)$$

Reducing each phase resistance will hence improve the overall gas transfer rate of the oxygenator. However, the magnitude of each resistance is not the same. For instance, the gas phase resistance is negligible¹⁶⁷, while the blood phase boundary layer resistance is the highest and can be 100 times larger than the membrane resistance^{167,168}. This phenomenon is particularly important in gas/liquid transfers in the laminar flow regimes. The absence of turbulences in the blood flow creates a boundary layer at the blood/membrane interface with increasing concentrations of gases that are not removed by convection (Figure 4). This saturated layer at the membrane surface acts like a diffusional barrier to the gas transfer reducing the transfer rate and keeping the gas transfer efficiency below the technical possibilities of the membrane.

This was confirmed also by the work of Vacanti's group¹⁶⁹ who tested the gas transfer in a microfluidic oxygenator across three different membranes: dense poly(dimethyl siloxane) (PDMS) membranes (63 μm and 12 μm thick) and porous polycarbonate (PC) with pore size of 1 μm . The gas transfer for all three membranes was in the same range, confirming that the bottleneck in the blood oxygenation performance is the mass transfer rate in the blood phase rather than the permeance of the membrane. This highlights the importance of an optimized and efficient blood module design.

Figure 4: Scheme of the diffusional boundary layer on a flat membrane. P_w is the gas partial pressure at the membrane wall, P_b is the gas partial pressure in blood; (modified from ref.166).

4.3 Membrane materials

4.3.1 Microporous membranes for ECMO

In 1960, McCaughan *et al.*¹⁷⁰ proposed for the first time microporous materials as candidates for membrane oxygenators in CPB. They tested membranes made of polyethylene, sintered nickel, and cellulose acetate-based polymers with a pore diameter of 1–10 μm . Although through pores increased the efficiency of gas exchange by providing direct contact of blood with air, significant plasma leakage and a high risk of air embolism were noted.

The first generation of blood oxygenators based on porous membranes was developed only after the appearance in the 1980s of hydrophobic polypropylene (PP) membranes with submicron pores for ultrafiltration. These membranes have excellent gas permeance, a porosity of up to 55% with a pore diameter of up to 0.03 μm ¹⁷¹, and a hydrophobic surface energy that prevents the penetration of plasma into the pores. However, porous PP membranes have a short lifetime of only several hours^{166,172} after which the gas permeance is reduced by membrane wetting (Figure 5). Indeed, the adsorption of plasma proteins onto the pore's surface increases the surface energy of the material, eventually allowing the plasma to break through¹⁵⁴.

4.3.2 Current ECMO membranes

Further efforts in membrane technology led in the early 2000s to the development of the second generation of blood oxygenators based on poly(4-methyl-1-pentene) (PMP) membranes. Compared to porous PP membranes, where gas molecules can freely permeate through, PMP membranes possess an asymmetric sponge-like structure with a dense hydrophobic outer skin. The high porosity and uniform pore distribution in the membrane's inner wall ensure high permeability of oxygen and carbon dioxide, while the thin non-porous outer skin avoids direct contact of liquids and gas. Thanks to PMP's high intrinsic gas permeability, reduced plasma leakages, and the possibility of operating for several weeks^{172,173}, PMP became the most widely used membrane material for long-term ECMO.

Overall, in current clinical practice, different types of membrane oxygenators are employed with respect to the duration of the therapy, namely, oxygenators with PP microporous membranes for short-term operations as CPB, and oxygenators with PMP nonporous membranes for long-term use.

4.3.3 Non-porous membranes for microfluidic oxygenators

The discovery of the excellent gas transfer capacity of silicone rubber by Kammermeyer in 1957 led the way toward a new type of non-porous membrane for gas exchange processes¹⁷⁴. Shortly after Kolobow *et al.*¹⁷⁵, Bramson *et al.*¹⁷⁶, Landé *et al.*¹⁷⁷, and others started producing and commercializing the first silicon membrane oxygenators. In 1971, Kolobow *et al.*¹⁷⁸ improved their disposable coil oxygenator which has been successfully used in

the clinical field until the development of PP and PMP porous membrane oxygenators (Figure 5).

transformation, surface methyl groups are removed and replaced with hydroxyl groups (SiO₂). Studies from Markov *et al.*¹⁸² and Houston *et al.*¹⁸³ revealed that the SiO₂ layer created by plasma treatment on the exposed surface significantly impedes the

Figure 5: Timeline of the development of ECMO membranes. The main advantages and disadvantages of each membrane generation are reported.

In microfluidic blood oxygenators, PDMS is the material of choice to fabricate flat nonporous membranes due to its excellent permeability to oxygen and carbon dioxide (PO₂: 800 Barrer, PCO₂: 3800 Barrer at 35°C¹⁷⁹) and its ease of microfabrication by spin coating or casting.

Even though the gas permeability is an intrinsic property of the material, in the case of PDMS membranes the fabrication method, as well as surface treatments, can influence the arrangement of polymer chains, increasing or reducing the free volumes that allow gas diffusion inside the network, thus impacting the final gas permeability of the membrane.

Lamberti *et al.*¹⁸⁰ investigated the effect of PDMS composition, i.e., the ratio between PDMS oligomers and curing agent, on its permeation properties to air. They focused on three membrane compositions: 5:1, 10:1, and 20:1 weight ratio of polymer base to curing agent and observed that increasing the polymer/curing agent ratio, the permeability of the membrane increases. This is due to a lower amount of cross-linked PDMS oligomers which allows an easier and faster diffusion of gases across the membrane. However, a PDMS membrane with a lower curing agent ratio is also more elastic, sticky, and harder to handle and integrate into a microfluidic device.

Berean *et al.*¹⁸¹ evaluated the gas permeation of PDMS membranes with respect to the crosslinking temperature of PDMS during synthesis. They compared five curing temperatures from 25°C to 150°C, and the result revealed an optimum temperature of 75 °C at which the permeability increased for all gasses tested.

Surface treatments and storage conditions of PDMS membranes also influence their gas permeability. A common treatment to convert PDMS surface from a hydrophobic to a hydrophilic state is the exposure to oxygen or air plasma. As part of such a

diffusion of oxygen through PDMS. Moreover, Markov and colleagues also investigated the effect of storage conditions after treatment. They found that the PDMS completely recovered its original permeability after a 3-day storage in air, while the gas diffusion barrier remained significant for up to 3 weeks if PDMS was maintained in contact with water.

Recently, new PDMS-based membranes have been developed for microfluidic blood oxygenators including reinforced PDMS membranes with ultrathin stainless-steel mesh^{184,185} or porous PTFE¹⁵⁸ or PSF¹⁸⁶ substrates to increase the mechanical strength, as well as PDMS membranes with patterned micro or nanopores to enhance gas diffusion^{187,188}.

In summary, PDMS advantages in terms of biocompatibility, gas permeability, and plasma non-leakage properties make it the dominant material for microfluidic oxygenator dense membranes. Nevertheless, the performances of PDMS membranes, most importantly its hemocompatibility, yet need to be tested in long-term studies.

4.3.4 Emerging material candidates

The latest studies identified and tested new classes of polymers such as polyester, polycellulose, and fluoropolymer as new candidate materials for a new generation of ECMO membranes. Fluoropolymers such as PTFE and PVDF (or PVDF-co-HFP) demonstrated to be highly promising due to their hydrophobic, oleophobic, and low surface energy properties which inhibit undesirable protein adsorption and prevent the cascade reaction of immune response and blood coagulation^{189–191}. In Park *et al.*¹⁹¹ work, the PVDF-co-HFP membrane coated with Hyflon AD60X (a fluoropolymer with extremely low surface energy) showed competitive performance in terms of blood oxygenation, low

protein adsorption, and absence of hemolysis, compared to commercial polyolefin membranes (PMP). However, processing PTFE polymer into a thin, hollow fibre shape is still technically challenging due to its high melt viscosity.

4.4 Microfluidic blood oxygenators

To date, various small-scale microfluidic artificial lung designs have been constructed and tested at lab scales^{158,169,184,185,192–208}. Microfluidic artificial lungs are commonly formed by a single blood layer and a single gas layer separated by a gas diffusion membrane. One of the first examples was the flat-plate membrane oxygenator developed by Hung *et al.*²⁰³ in 1977. Despite Hung's pioneering work, the important hydraulic resistance of the small-diameter blood channels and the advent of hollow fiber membrane technology delayed the research in microfluidic artificial lungs.

In 2008, Lee *et al.*^{204,209,210} introduced theoretical models to study the suitability of different designs for microfluidic blood oxygenators with various heights and geometries²⁰⁹. They implemented two small-scale prototypes; one of the designs featured an array of 15 μm -tall, rectangular blood channels, and a 130 μm -thick PDMS gas exchange membrane and was successfully tested on porcine blood. They predicted that a scale-up version able to oxygenate a blood flow of 4 L min⁻¹ could have a priming volume as small as 13 ml and a total volume of 252 cm³ not including manifolds²⁰⁴.

In the following years, many research groups developed and tested new micro-oxygenators. Particularly of note is the work of Hoganson *et al.*²⁰⁶ who created a microfluidic lung assist device with a 9 μm -thick silicon membrane and a 100 μm -tall, blood channels network with physiological blood flow. They applied the natural branching and scaling as described by Murray's law²¹¹, coupled with iterative computational fluid dynamic analysis to create a vascular network with uniform flow at bifurcations, biomimetic vessel length, and shear stress in the arterial range. However, the limitation to a single channel height throughout the entire network imposed by photolithography limited the gas exchange efficiency of the microchannels.

In the attempt to improve the overall gas transfer efficiency of the microfluidic artificial lungs, Burgess *et al.*²¹² in 2009, stacked two blood and four gas channel layers fabricating for the first time a microfluidic oxygenator with double-sided diffusion of oxygen into the blood channels. Successively, Dabaghi *et al.*^{158,185,200} among others^{194,199,213} adopted this promising approach. In 2018, Dabaghi's group developed a microfluidic membrane oxygenator with double-sided gas transfer microchannels with the capability of being operated in a pumpless manner¹⁸⁵. Oxygen uptake in the double-sided device was increased by up to 343% compared to the single-sided device with the same design. They then assembled 4 devices to build a lung assist device (LAD) for preterm neonates with respiratory distress syndrome. The LAD could provide adequate oxygenation up to a blood flow rate of 60 ml/min using pure oxygen with a pressure drop low enough (10–

51 mmHg) to enable a pumpless operation (Figure 6).

Recently, the same research group further ameliorated this approach by introducing for the first time a micro-oxygenator with four-sided oxygen diffusion²⁰¹. Their novel design included embedded hollow air chambers between blood microchannels to involve also the side walls in gas exchange, increasing the gas exchange surface area without affecting blood flow characteristics or the channel's geometry. Compared with its equivalent double-sided gas exchange design, the new design's performance is enhanced by up to 223%. Although proof of concept has been demonstrated for this new configuration, a more reliable fabrication approach needs to be developed, and the robustness of the device must be further evaluated (Figure 6).

A different technique was adopted by Femmer *et al.*²¹⁴ to enhance oxygen uptake in the blood channels. They used passive micromixers and chaotic advection principles to mix the fluid as it travels through a channel and increase oxygen mass transfer in the blood phase. Staggered herringbone micromixer structures with 50 μm depth and 125 μm width were patterned on channels in groups of six. Although this design demonstrated the reduction of oxygen diffusion resistance in blood, the advection phenomena may produce zones of high shear stress as well as stagnation zones along the microchannel which can lead to clot formation.

Toward the direction of truly portable artificial lungs, the work of Wu *et al.*¹⁹² and Rochow *et al.*¹⁹³ must be cited. Wu *et al.*¹⁹² designed the microfluidic oxygenator units in which the gas side of the membrane was directly exposed to air, thus eliminating the need for a ventilating gas supply.

Rochow *et al.*¹⁹³ subsequently arranged in parallel 10 oxygenator units and tested the resulting LAD *in vitro* and *in vivo* in two newborn piglets. The heart pressure was sufficient to drive the blood flow and the oxygen exchange was 30 ml/min m² at a blood flow rate of up to 1.6 L/min m². Although the results of Rochow's group support the feasibility of a pumpless microfluidic artificial lung efficient with ambient air, the hemocompatibility of the device and its lifetime in *in vivo* testing must be further assessed.

The best performance in terms of throughput has recently been achieved by Santos *et al.*²¹⁵ and Vedula *et al.*²¹⁶ who developed a biomimetic multilayer device capable of saturating porcine venous blood at flow rates up to 200 ml/min, the highest of any microfluidic oxygenator to date.

A summary of microfluidic artificial lungs in the literature is given in Table 2. Four parameters describe the design: blood channel height (H), membrane material, membrane thickness (δm), and gas exchange surface area. While three parameters describe the oxygenator performances: blood flow rate, oxygen transfer, and pressure drop (ΔP). Data on gas exchange represent the maximum values reported.

Figure 6: Microfluidic artificial lungs. **A)** Schematic view of the artificial placenta-type microfluidic blood oxygenator (APMBO) developed by Debaghi et al. Picture of the lung assist device consisting of 4 APMBO units in parallel, and SEM image of the cross section showing the double-sided membrane design. (Reproduced from Ref. 186 with permission from the Royal Society of Chemistry.) **B)** Assembled hemocompatible, biomimetic microfluidic blood oxygenator by J. Santos et al. with detail of the cross-section showing blood and an oxygen channel separated by a 50-micron gas transfer membrane. SEM image of branching channel junction with varying channel depth.²¹⁶ **C)** Schematic top view of the circular network of blood microcapillaries by Lachaux et al. and SEM image of the cross-view showing the PDMS trilayer structure.²⁰³ (B and C are licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.)

Table 2. Summary of published works on microfluidic artificial lungs.

Source	H (μm)	Membrane material	δm (μm)	Surface area (cm ²)	Supply gas	Blood flow (ml/min)	O ₂ transfer (ml/min m ²)	ΔP (mmHg)
Lee 2008 ²⁰⁴	15	PDMS	130	0.83	O ₂ Air	1.87 0.75	256 85	4
Hoganson 2010 ¹⁶⁹	200	porous PC PDMS/PC PDMS	12 12 63	18	O ₂	8	136 145 151	123
Potkay 2011 ²⁰⁵	20 10	PDMS	15	2.34 1.67	Air	1.5	137 225	500 -
Hoganson 2011 ²⁰⁶	100	PDMS	9	6.93	O ₂	6.3	41	20
Kniazeva 2012 ²⁰⁸	50	PDMS	30	-	O ₂	10	329	-
	100		30				317	
	50		117				223	
Wu 2013 ²¹⁷	80	μporous PDMS	20	15.26	Air	4	19	25
Rochow 2014 ¹⁹³	80	PDMS	20	152.6	O ₂	40	104	63
					Air		31	
Rieper 2015 ¹⁹⁴	100	PDMS	90	1200	O ₂	50	25	80
					Air		13	
Gimbel 2016 ¹⁹⁵	100	PDMS	30	46.23	O ₂	25	260	-
Thompson 2017 ¹⁹⁶	10	PDMS	66	-	O ₂	1.25	153	120
					Air		0.25	
Matharoo 2018 ¹⁸⁴	170 - 60	PDMS + steel mesh	50	221.7	Air	48	41	50
Dabaghi 2018 ¹⁹⁷	130	PTFE + PDMS	110 - 25	42.79 65.3 99.43	Air	5 16 20	35	33 70 50
	100				O ₂		113	
	160				O ₂		80	
Thompson 2019 ¹⁹⁸	30	PDMS	30	31.5	O ₂	25	127	66
Malankowska 2019 ¹⁹⁹	100	PDMS	120	2.9	O ₂	1	92	-
Dabaghi 2019 ¹⁵⁸	160	PDMS	120 - 30	800	O ₂	150 60	56	132 46
			30		Air		45	
Dabaghi 2020 ²⁰¹	70	PTFE + PDMS	110 - 25	2.3	O ₂	2.56 1.28	125	-
			25		Air		37	
Lachaux 2021 ²⁰²	105	PDMS	15	53.5	O ₂	80	490	80
Vedula 2022 ²¹⁶	200	PDMS	50	1063.2	O ₂	240	113	230
Isenberg 2023 ²¹⁸	160	PDMS	50	1336	O ₂	750	164	51

To conclude, it is important to reiterate that the key bottleneck is not the permselectivity of the membrane (although better performance is still desired), but the hemocompatibility of the membrane material to increase the device lifetime. The

development of a compliant, resistant, hemocompatible, and superamphiphobic membrane will be an important breakthrough²¹⁹. In addition, especially for microfluidic artificial lungs, particular effort should be devoted to creating a

biomimetic blood module design that improves the mass transfer coefficient of gasses.

5. Conclusions

Membrane technology is the central component in many fields of life science as artificial organs, tissue engineering, medical equipment, and in vitro blood diagnosis. Microfluidics has developed into a promising research direction for miniaturization and improvement of analytical chemistry and bioscience processes. Combining membrane technologies with microfluidics can promote better developments in both fields.

This manuscript reviews applications of membrane-based microfluidics in life science, focusing on organs-on-chip and microfluidic artificial organs.

5.1 Conclusive remarks on membranes for organs-on-chip

The tables clearly show the different efforts put into the recapitulation of the physiological conditions in terms of biological components and mechanical stimuli, compared to the recreation of a relevant model of the native basement membrane. Indeed, despite the great advancement in OOC technologies with new materials, better actuators and sensors, and a rapidly expanding library of different organs on a chip, the advance in the development of biomimetic porous membranes is very slow. The main limitations that need to be addressed for the creation of more physiologically relevant membrane models are:

- **Membrane thickness.** Microfabricated membranes from non-natural polymers are too thick to be representative of the native ultrathin basement membrane (20-50 nm)²²⁰. In addition to a better mimic of physiological separation, thinner membranes also enable higher hydraulic and diffusive permeability^{221,222} and lower background TEER²²³.
- **Membrane surface.** A smooth surface with artificial pores poorly replicates the fibrillar structure of the in vivo basement membrane²²⁰; it alters the topographical cues increasing the possibility of changing the original cell phenotype²²⁴.
- **Membrane stiffness.** The polymers presented in this chapter (with PDMS being an exception) possess a high elastic modulus in the GPa range which is significantly stiffer than the native BM. On the other hand, the use of natural biodegradable polymers and hydrogels with low elastic modulus raises the issue of insufficient mechanical stability of the free-standing membranes over time.

Along with the stated considerations, the manufacturing, handling, and integration of a free-standing ultrathin membrane with low stiffness into microfluidic devices is still challenging. Researchers must keep in mind that for OoC to reach their goal of drug testing devices, it is required to improve the accuracy and consistency of these microfluidic models, while enabling serial production. Indeed, the manufacture of thousands of devices per day will be necessary to meet a possible future demand of pharmaceutical industries. Instead, to date, the

manufacturing process of organs-on-chip can be considered as artisanal, where each device is made by hand, at a maximum production throughput of several devices per day. For this to happen novel cost-effective materials and novel fabrication techniques should be adopted²²⁵.

In conclusion, to date, no widely accepted material or method can meet all the requirements. Designing an artificial membrane that can provide biochemical, biophysical, topographical, and mechanical cues while can also address technical fabrication issues is highly necessary.

5.2 Conclusive remarks on artificial lungs

Through microfabrication techniques, it is possible to create artificial blood networks with feature sizes that are comparable to those in the natural lungs. This substantially increases the efficiency of gas exchange and decreases the blood prime volume of microfluidic artificial lungs in comparison with commercial oxygenators. However, despite their efficiency, two main hurdles still need to be addressed for microfluidic artificial lungs to become a clinical reality: long-term hemocompatibility and scalability.

- **Hemocompatibility.** ECMO clinical applications require artificial lung lifetimes of up to several months (i.e. lung failure or chronic lung disease) and up to now, microfluidic artificial lungs have not demonstrated this level of hemocompatibility. Though they can better mimic the vascular physiology, the impact on blood compatibility has not yet been quantified.

The development of microfluidic artificial lungs for long-term application should include:

- 1) A compliant membrane module with flexible yet resistant polymer membranes that are mechanically similar to the blood-gas membrane in the lung. These novel membranes would deflect compensating changes in pulmonary blood pressure and recreate cylindrical-like vascular geometries eliminating blood stagnation zones at the corners of the microchannels²²⁶.
- 2) An optimized vascular network coupled with effective surface modifications and coatings to minimize the foreign body response of the device²²⁷. The functions of the heart and arteries are mechanical rather than chemical, thus an effort to recreate in the systems the forces and stresses produced by the blood flow on the walls of the cardiovascular vessels is mandatory. The blood flow path should reproduce the circular vascular channels geometry, follow natural scaling and branching laws, and exhibit velocities and shear stress in a physiological range.

Finally, it is crucial to prove the effective blood damage of microfluidic artificial lungs in long-term studies in animal models and eventually in clinical trials.

- **Scalability.** The scalability issue in microfluidic artificial organs consists of two main points: the low throughput of the microfluidic devices, and the poor scale-up possibilities of the current manufacturing techniques and materials.

To meet the high throughput required at the clinical level, the challenge for microfluidic oxygenators is to enhance their gas exchange performance at higher blood flow rates (up to 4-7 L/min). To do so, the combination of two approaches is necessary: 1) fabricating devices with larger gas exchange surface area (i.e., not only one or two-sided gas exchange) to improve the oxygenation capacity of a single device and 2) parallelization of several devices to increase the overall throughput. Although the work of Santos *et al.*²¹⁵ demonstrated a single device capable of achieving a reasonable oxygen transfer at a blood flow rate of 30 ml/min, further improvements must still be made toward the goal of treating adult blood flow rates with physiological shear rates and pressure drops.

Moreover, the applicability of microfluidic blood oxygenators at a clinical scale is closely tied to the available manufacturing technologies and materials. Current microfabrication techniques are labour-intensive, limiting the production rates, and based on fabrication methods that limit channel depth to a single level. In addition, all the microfluidic devices proposed up to now are produced by lithography methods, which impair the creation of circular channels, and are made of PDMS which makes them not compatible with the actual mass-production techniques. A promising solution may be high-resolution 3D printing or precision computer numerical control (CNC) machining since they are capable of fabrication at the microscale level with great degree of freedom in size and 3D designs. Other authors suggested some unconventional techniques, for instance, using lubricant-infused mould, combining PDMS membrane with SU-8 and quartz or developing materials or hybrid microfluidic structures with better performances than PDMS for biomedical applications²²⁸.

Author Contributions

STC conceived and wrote the original draft. GN, TF, JBB, ER and GMS contributed in reviewing the manuscript. CP, CMP, and JV structured and reviewed the manuscript, and managed the projects. All authors contributed to the article and approved the submitted version.

Conflicts of interest

Authors STC, GN, TF, CMP, JBB, ER, and CP were employed by the company Eden Tech.

The authors not stated earlier affirm that the study was conducted without any existing commercial or financial associations that could be perceived as a potential conflict of interest.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported in part by the IPANEMA project, which received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 872662.

S.T.C. has received funding from SmartAge project, the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 859890.

References

1. Cottet, J. & Renaud, P. *Introduction to microfluidics. Drug Delivery Devices and Therapeutic Systems* (Elsevier Inc., 2020).
2. Kuo, J. S. & Chiu, D. T. Controlling Mass Transport in Microfluidic Devices. *Annu. Rev. Anal. Chem.* **2011**, 275–296 (2017).
3. Aubry, G., Lee, H. J. & Lu, H. Advances in Microfluidics: Technical Innovations and Applications in Diagnostics and Therapeutics. *Anal. Chem.* **95**, 444–467 (2023).
4. Sun, M. *et al.* Advances in Micro / Nanoporous Membranes for Biomedical Engineering. *Adv. Healthc. Mater.* **10**, 1–19 (2021).
5. Yan, B., Zhang, Y., Li, Z., Zhou, P. & Mao, Y. Electrospun nanofibrous membrane for biomedical application. *SN Appl. Sci.* **4**, (2022).
6. Mallakpour, S. & Azadi, E. Nanofiltration membranes for food and pharmaceutical industries. *Emergent Mater.* 1329–1343 (2022)
7. Papaioannou, E. H. *et al.* Agri-Food Industry Waste as Resource of Chemicals: The Role of Membrane Technology in Their Sustainable Recycling. *Sustainability* **14**, (2022).
8. Lu, N. *et al.* Label-free microfluidic cell sorting and detection for rapid blood analysis. *Lab Chip* **23**, 1226–1257 (2023).
9. Coelho, B. *et al.* Digital Microfluidics for Nucleic Acid Amplification. *Sensors* **17**, 1495 (2017).
10. Pittman, T. W., Decsi, D. B., Punyadeera, C. & Henry, C. S. Saliva-based microfluidic point-of-care diagnostic. *Theranostics* **13**, 1091 (2023).
11. Vidic, J. *et al.* Point-of-Need DNA Testing for Detection of Foodborne Pathogenic Bacteria. *Sensors* **19**, (2019).
12. Kotsiri, Z., Vidic, J. & Vantarakis, A. Applications of biosensors for bacteria and virus detection in food and water – A systematic review. *J. Environ. Sci.* **111**, 367–379 (2022).
13. Esch, M. B. *et al.* On chip porous polymer membranes for integration of gastrointestinal tract epithelium with microfluidic 'body-on-a-chip' devices. *Biomed. Microdevices* **14**, 895–906 (2012).
14. Raimondi, I. *et al.* Organ-On-A-Chip in vitro Models of the Brain and the Blood-Brain Barrier and Their Value to Study the Microbiota-Gut-Brain Axis in Neurodegeneration. *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* **7**, (2020).

15. Stucki, A. O. *et al.* A lung-on-a-chip array with an integrated bio-inspired respiration mechanism. *Lab Chip* **15**, 1302–1310 (2015).
16. Salimbeigi, G., Vrana, N. E., Ghaemmaghami, A. M., Huri, P. Y. & McGuinness, G. B. Basement membrane properties and their recapitulation in organ-on-chip applications. *Mater. Today Bio* **15**, (2022).
17. Vermaak, L., Neomagus, H. W. J. P. & Bessarabov, D. G. Recent Advances in Membrane-Based Electrochemical Hydrogen Separation : A Review. *Membranes (Basel)*. **11**, (2021).
18. Ulbricht, M. Advanced functional polymer membranes. *Polymer (Guildf)*. **47**, 2217–2262 (2006).
19. Wijmans, J. G. & Baker, R. W. The solution-diffusion model: a review. *J. Memb. Sci.* **107**, 1–21 (1995).
20. Couper, J. R., Roy, P. W. & Stanley M., W. Chapter 19 - Membrane Separations. in *Chemical Process Equipment* (eds. Couper, J. R., Penney, W. R., Fair, J. R. & Walas, S. M. B. T.-C. P. E. (Revised S. E.) 663–690 (Gulf Professional Publishing, 2010).
21. Matteucci, S., Yampolskii, Y., Freeman, B. D. & Pinnau, I. Chapter 1: Transport of Gases and Vapors in Glassy and Rubbery Polymers. in *Materials Science of Membranes for Gas and Vapor Separation* (eds. Yampolskii, Y., Pinnau, I. & Freeman, B. D.) 1–40 (2006).
22. Wang, M. *et al.* Relationship between polymer – filler interfaces in separation layers and gas transport properties of mixed matrix composite membranes. *J. Memb. Sci.* **495**, 252–268 (2015).
23. Aghaebrahimian, R., Biniiaz, P., Zakeri, S. M. E. & Rahimpour, M. R. Chapter 9 - Transport phenomena in membrane contactor systems. in *Current Trends and Future Developments on (Bio-) Membranes* (eds. Basile, A., Ghasemzadeh, K. & Iulianelli, A. B. T.-C. T. and F. D. on (Bio-) M.) 209–229 (Elsevier, 2022).
24. Oyama, S. T., Yamada, M., Sugawara, T., Takagaki, A. & Kikuchi, R. Review on Mechanisms of Gas Permeation through Inorganic Membranes. *J. Japan Pet. Inst.* **54**, 298–309 (2011).
25. Sotirchos, S. V & Burganos, V. N. Transport of Gases in Porous Membranes. *MRS Bull.* 41–45 (1999).
26. Mehta, A. & Zydney, A. L. Permeability and selectivity analysis for ultrafiltration membranes. *J. Memb. Sci.* **249**, 245–249 (2005).
27. De Jong, J., Lammertink, R. G. H. & Wessling, M. Membranes and microfluidics: A review. *Lab Chip* **6**, 1125–1139 (2006).
28. Schneider, S., Gruner, D., Richter, A. & Loskill, P. Membrane integration into PDMS-free microfluidic platforms for organ-on-chip and analytical chemistry applications. *Lab Chip* **21**, 1866–1885 (2021).
29. Paskan, T., Grijpma, D., Stamatialis, D. & Poot, A. Flat and microstructured polymeric membranes in organs-on-chips. *J. R. Soc. Interface* **15**, (2018).
30. Reardon, S. ‘Organs-on-chips’ go mainstream. *Nature* **523**, 266 (2015).
31. Ingber, D. E. Human organs-on-chips for disease modelling, drug development and personalized medicine. *Nat. Rev. Genet.* **23**, 467–491 (2022).
32. Occhetta, P. *et al.* Hyperphysiological compression of articular cartilage induces an osteoarthritic phenotype in a cartilage-on-a-chip model. *Nat. Biomed. Eng.* **3**, 545–557 (2019).
33. Marsano, A. *et al.* Beating heart on a chip: A novel microfluidic platform to generate functional 3D cardiac microtissues. *Lab Chip* **16**, 599–610 (2016).
34. Park, S. H. *et al.* Chip-Based Comparison of the Osteogenesis of Human Bone Marrow- and Adipose Tissue-Derived Mesenchymal Stem Cells under Mechanical Stimulation. *PLoS One* **7**, 1–11 (2012).
35. Dowling, D. P., Miller, I. S., Ardhaoui, M. & Gallagher, W. M. Effect of surface wettability and topography on the adhesion of osteosarcoma cells on plasma-modified polystyrene. *J. Biomater. Appl.* **26**, 327–347 (2011).
36. Kunzler, T. P., Drobek, T., Schuler, M. & Spencer, N. D. Systematic study of osteoblast and fibroblast response to roughness by means of surface-morphology gradients. *Biomaterials* **28**, 2175–2182 (2007).
37. Lange, R. *et al.* Cell-extracellular matrix interaction and physico-chemical characteristics of titanium surfaces depend on the roughness of the material. *Biomol. Eng.* **19**, 255–261 (2002).
38. Tong, C. Y. & Derek, C. J. C. Membrane surface roughness promotes rapid initial cell adhesion and long term microalgal biofilm stability. *Environ. Res.* **206**, 112602 (2022).
39. Zhou, K. *et al.* Nano-micrometer surface roughness gradients reveal topographical influences on differentiating responses of vascular cells on biodegradable magnesium. *Bioact. Mater.* **6**, 262–272 (2021).
40. Majhy, B., Priyadarshini, P. & Sen, A. K. Effect of surface energy and roughness on cell adhesion and growth-facile surface modification for enhanced cell culture. *RSC Adv.* **11**, 15467–15476 (2021).
41. Chen, C. S., Mrksich, M., Huang, S., Whitesides, G. M. & Ingber, D. E. Geometric control of cell life and death. *Science (80-)*. **276**, 1425–1428 (1997).
42. Hulsman, M. *et al.* Analysis of high-throughput screening reveals the effect of surface topographies on cellular morphology. *Acta Biomater.* **15**, 29–38 (2015).
43. Esch, M. B., Post, D. J., Shuler, M. L. & Stokol, T. Characterization of in vitro endothelial linings grown within microfluidic channels. *Tissue Eng. - Part A* **17**, 2965–2971 (2011).
44. Broaders, K. E., Cerchiari, A. E. & Gartner, Z. J. Coupling between apical tension and basal adhesion allow epithelia to collectively sense and respond to substrate topography over long distances. *Integr. Biol. (United Kingdom)* **7**, 1611–1621 (2015).
45. Altay, G., Tosi, S., García-Díaz, M. & Martínez, E. Imaging the Cell Morphological Response to 3D Topography and Curvature in Engineered Intestinal Tissues. *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* **8**, 1–12 (2020).
46. Galván-Chacón, V. P. *et al.* Decoupling the role of chemistry and microstructure in hMSCs response to an osteoinductive calcium phosphate ceramic. *Bioact. Mater.* **19**, 127–138 (2023).
47. Peng, S. W., Li, C. W., Chiu, I. M. & Wang, G. J. Nerve guidance conduit with a hybrid structure of a PLGA microfibrillar bundle wrapped in a micro/nanostructured membrane. *Int. J. Nanomedicine* **12**, 421–432 (2017).
48. Engler, A. J., Sen, S., Sweeney, H. L. & Discher, D. E. Matrix Elasticity Directs Stem Cell Lineage Specification. *Cell* **126**, 677–689 (2006).
49. Das, P. *et al.* Tunable Microstructured Membranes in Organs-on-Chips to Monitor Transendothelial Hydraulic Resistance. *Tissue Eng. - Part A* **25**, 1635–1645 (2019).

50. Ye, K. *et al.* Matrix Stiffness and Nanoscale Spatial Organization of Cell-Adhesive Ligands Direct Stem Cell Fate. *Nano Lett.* **15**, 4720–4729 (2015).
51. Yi, B., Xu, Q. & Liu, W. An overview of substrate stiffness guided cellular response and its applications in tissue regeneration. *Bioact. Mater.* **15**, 82–102 (2022).
52. Zan, F. *et al.* Role of Stiffness versus Wettability in Regulating Cell Behaviors on Polymeric Surfaces. *ACS Biomater. Sci. Eng.* **6**, 912–922 (2020).
53. Gil-Redondo, J. C., Weber, A., Zbiral, B., Vivanco, M. d. M. & Toca-Herrera, J. L. Substrate stiffness modulates the viscoelastic properties of MCF-7 cells. *J. Mech. Behav. Biomed. Mater.* **125**, (2022).
54. Bosworth, A. M. *et al.* Influence of Substrate Stiffness on Barrier Function in an iPSC-Derived In Vitro Blood-Brain Barrier Model. *Cell. Mol. Bioeng.* **15**, 31–42 (2022).
55. Camarero-Espinosa, S. *et al.* 3D Printed Dual-Porosity Scaffolds: The Combined Effect of Stiffness and Porosity in the Modulation of Macrophage Polarization. *Adv. Healthc. Mater.* **11**, 1–16 (2022).
56. Zhou, S. wen *et al.* The substrate stiffness at physiological range significantly modulates vascular cell behavior. *Colloids Surfaces B Biointerfaces* **214**, 112483 (2022).
57. Park, J. S. *et al.* The Effect of Matrix Stiffness on the Differentiation of Mesenchymal Stem Cells in Response to TGF- β . *Biomaterials* **32**, 3921–3930 (2011).
58. Wen, J. H. *et al.* Interplay of matrix stiffness and protein tethering in stem cell differentiation. *Nat. Mater.* **13**, 979–987 (2014).
59. Al-Azzam, N. & Alazzam, A. Micropatterning of cells via adjusting surface wettability using plasma treatment and graphene oxide deposition. *PLoS One* **17**, 1–14 (2022).
60. Ferrari, M., Cirisano, F. & Carmen Morán, M. Mammalian Cell Spheroids on Mixed Organic–Inorganic Superhydrophobic Coating. *Molecules* **27**, (2022).
61. Khang, G., Rhee, J. M., Lee, J. H., Lee, I. & Lee, H. B. Interaction of Different Types of Cells on Poly(L-lactide-co-glycolide) Surface with Wettability Chemogradient. *Korea Polym. J.* **8**, 276–284 (2000).
62. Premnath, P., Tavangar, A., Tan, B. & Venkatakrishnan, K. Tuning cell adhesion by direct nanostructuring silicon into cell repulsive/adhesive patterns. *Exp. Cell Res.* **337**, 44–52 (2015).
63. Casillo, S. M., Peredo, A. P., Perry, S. J., Chung, H. H. & Gaborski, T. R. Membrane Pore Spacing Can Modulate Endothelial Cell-Substrate and Cell-Cell Interactions. *ACS Biomater. Sci. Eng.* **3**, 243–248 (2017).
64. Chung, H. H., Mireles, M., Kwarta, B. J. & Gaborski, T. R. Use of porous membranes in tissue barrier and co-culture models. *Lab Chip* **18**, 1671–1689 (2018).
65. Swanson, W. B. *et al.* Macropore design of tissue engineering scaffolds regulates mesenchymal stem cell differentiation fate. *Biomaterials* **272**, 120769 (2021).
66. Maoz, B. M. *et al.* Organs-on-Chips with combined multi-electrode array and transepithelial electrical resistance measurement capabilities. *Lab Chip* **17**, 2294–2302 (2017).
67. Shim, K., Lee, D., Han, J. & Nguyen, N. Microfluidic gut-on-a-chip with three-dimensional villi structure. *Biomed. Microdevices* **19**, (2017).
68. Abhyankar, V. V., Wu, M., Koh, C. & Hatch, A. V. A Reversibly Sealed, Easy Access, Modular (SEAM) Microfluidic Architecture to Establish In Vitro Tissue Interfaces. *PLoS One* **26**, 1–20 (2016).
69. Jang, K.-J. *et al.* Human kidney proximal tubule-on-a-chip for drug transport and nephrotoxicity assessment. *Integr. Biol. (Camb)*. **5**, 1119–1129 (2013).
70. Maschmeyer, I. *et al.* Chip-based human liver–intestine and liver–skin co-cultures – A first step toward systemic repeated dose substance testing in vitro. *Eur J Pharm Biopharm.* **95(Pt A)**, 77–87 (2015).
71. Wagner, I. *et al.* A dynamic multi-organ-chip for long-term cultivation and substance testing proven by 3D human liver and skin tissue co-culture. *Lab Chip* **13**, 3538–3547 (2013).
72. Zhu, L. *et al.* A vertical-flow bioreactor array compacts hepatocytes for enhanced polarity and functions. *Lab Chip* **16**, 3898–3908 (2016).
73. Loskill, P. *et al.* WAT-on-a-chip: a physiologically relevant microfluidic system incorporating white adipose tissue. *Lab Chip* **17**, 1645–1654 (2017).
74. Lee, H. *et al.* A pumpless multi-organ-on-a-chip (MOC) combined with a pharmacokinetic-pharmacodynamic (PK-PD) model. *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* **114**, 432–443 (2017).
75. Husic, S. *et al.* Rapid prototyping of a multilayer microphysiological system for primary human intestinal epithelial culture. *bioRxiv* 400721 (2018).
76. Sticker, D., Rothbauer, M., Lechner, S., Hehenberger, M. & Ertl, P. Multilayered, membrane-integrated microfluidics based on replica molding of a thiol-ene epoxy thermoset for organ-on-a-chip applications. *Lab Chip* **15**, 4542–4554 (2015).
77. Ma, Y. *et al.* Microdroplet Chain Array for Cell Migration Assays. *Lab Chip* (2016)
78. Jie, M., Li, H., Lin, L., Zhang, J. & Lin, J. Integrated microfluidic system for cell co-culture and simulation of drug metabolism. *RSC Adv.* (2016)
79. Wang, Y. I., Abaci, H. E. & Shuler, M. L. Microfluidic blood-brain barrier model provides in vivo-like barrier properties for drug permeability screening. *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* **114**, 184–194 (2017).
80. Lee, S., Jin, S., Kim, Y. K., Sung, G. Y. & Chung, J. H. Construction of 3D multicellular microfluidic chip for an in vitro skin model. *Biomed. Microdevices* **19**, (2017).
81. Brown, J. A. *et al.* Metabolic consequences of inflammatory disruption of the blood-brain barrier in an organ-on-chip model of the human neurovascular unit. *J. Neuroinflammation* 1–17 (2016)
82. Li, Z. *et al.* Assessment of metabolism-dependent drug efficacy and toxicity on a multilayer organs-on-a-chip. *Integr. Biol.* **8**, 1022–1029 (2016).
83. van der Helm, M. W. *et al.* Direct quantification of transendothelial electrical resistance in organs-on-chips. *Biosens. Bioelectron.* **85**, 924–929 (2016).
84. Pocock, K. J. *et al.* Low-temperature bonding process for the fabrication of hybrid glass–membrane organ-on-a-chip devices. *J. Micro/Nanolithography, MEMS, MOEMS* **15**, 44502 (2016).
85. Rahimnejad, M. *et al.* Engineered Biomimetic Membranes for Organ-on-a-Chip. *ACS Biomater. Sci. Eng.* **8**, 5038–5059 (2022).

86. Wala, J., Maji, D. & Das, S. Influence of physico-mechanical properties of elastomeric material for different cell growth. *Biomed. Mater.* **12**, (2017).
87. Lee, M. *et al.* Surface Hydrophobicity Modulates the Key Characteristics of Cancer Spheroids through the Interaction with the Adsorbed Proteins. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **31**, 1–12 (2021).
88. Chen, M. *et al.* Naked Liquid Marbles: A Robust Three-Dimensional Low-Volume Cell-Culturing System. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **11**, 9814–9823 (2019).
89. Cui, X. *et al.* Tuning microenvironment for multicellular spheroid formation in thermo-responsive anionic microgel scaffolds. *J. Biomed. Mater. Res. - Part A* **106**, 2899–2909 (2018).
90. Azizpour, N., Avazpour, R., Sawan, M., Rosenzweig, D. H. & Ajji, A. Uniformity of spheroids-on-a-chip by surface treatment of PDMS microfluidic platforms. *Sensors & Diagnostics* **1**, 750–764 (2022).
91. Cecelja, M. & Chowienczyk, P. Role of arterial stiffness in cardiovascular disease. *JRSM Cardiovasc. Dis.* **1**, 1–10 (2012).
92. Mitchell, G. F. *et al.* Changes in arterial stiffness and wave reflection with advancing age in healthy men and women: The Framingham Heart Study. *Hypertension* **43**, 1239–1245 (2004).
93. Quinn, U., Tomlinson, L. A. & Cockcroft, J. R. Arterial stiffness. *J. R. Soc. Med. Cardiovasc. Dis. Soc. Med. Cardiovasc. Dis.* **50**, 39–44 (20012).
94. McMillan, A. H. *et al.* Rapid fabrication of membrane-integrated thermoplastic elastomer microfluidic devices. *Micromachines* **11**, 1–19 (2020).
95. Renous, N. *et al.* Spatial trans-epithelial electrical resistance (S-TEER) integrated in organs-on-chips. *Lab Chip* **22**, 71–79 (2022).
96. Baptista, D. *et al.* 3D Lung-on-Chip Model Based on Biomimetically Microcurved Culture Membranes. *ACS Biomater. Sci. Eng.* **8**, 2684–2699 (2022).
97. Liang, T. *et al.* Sensors and Actuators B : Chemical Microfluidic chip system integrated with light addressable potentiometric sensor (LAPS) for real-time extracellular acidification detection. *Sensors Actuators B. Chem.* **301**, 127004 (2019).
98. Jin, L. *et al.* Analyzing Human Periodontal Soft Tissue Inflammation and Drug Responses In Vitro Using Epithelium-Capillary Interface On-a-Chip. *Biosensors* **12**, (2022).
99. Brown, J. A. *et al.* Recreating blood-brain barrier physiology and structure on chip: A novel neurovascular microfluidic bioreactor. *Biomicrofluidics* **9**, 1–15 (2015).
100. Eain, M. M. G. *et al.* Engineering Solutions for Representative Models of the Gastrointestinal Human-Microbe Interface. *Engineering* **3**, 60–65 (2017).
101. Gao, D., Liu, H., Lin, J. M., Wang, Y. & Jiang, Y. Characterization of drug permeability in Caco-2 monolayers by mass spectrometry on a membrane-based microfluidic device. *Lab Chip* **13**, 978–985 (2013).
102. Maschmeyer, I. *et al.* European Journal of Pharmaceutics and Biopharmaceutics Chip-based human liver – intestine and liver – skin cocultures – A first step toward systemic repeated dose substance testing in vitro. *Eur. J. Pharm. Biopharm.* **95**, 77–87 (2015).
103. Wang, Y. I., Abaci, H. E. & Shuler, M. L. Microfluidic blood-brain barrier model provides in vivo-like barrier properties for drug permeability screening. *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* **114**, 184–194 (2017).
104. Bok, Y. *et al.* Liver Sinusoid on a Chip : Long-Term Layered Co-Culture of Primary Rat Hepatocytes and Endothelial Cells in Microfluidic Platforms. *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* **112**, 2571–2582 (2015).
105. Schuller, P. *et al.* A lab-on-a-chip system with an embedded porous membrane-based impedance biosensor array for nanoparticle risk assessment on placental Bewo trophoblast cells. *Sensors Actuators B. Chem.* **312**, 127946 (2020).
106. Lee, H., Kim, D. S., Ha, S. K., Choi, I. & Lee, J. M. A Pumpless Multi-Organ-on-a-Chip (MOC) Combined With a Pharmacokinetic – Pharmacodynamic (PK –PD) Model. *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* 1–12 (2016)
107. Loskill, P. *et al.* WAT-on-a-chip: A physiologically relevant microfluidic system incorporating white adipose tissue. *Lab Chip* (2017)
108. Maoz, B. M. *et al.* Organs-on-Chips with combined multi-electrode array and transepithelial electrical resistance measurement capabilities†. *Lab Chip* **17**, 2294–2302 (2017).
109. Shim, K. Y. *et al.* Microfluidic gut-on-a-chip with three-dimensional villi structure. *Biomed. Microdevices* **19**, (2017).
110. Persson, H. *et al.* Rapid assembly of PMMA microfluidic devices with PETE membranes for studying the endothelium. *Sensors Actuators B. Chem.* **356**, 131342 (2022).
111. Koch, E. V., Ledwig, V., Bendas, S., Reichl, S. & Dietzel, A. Tissue Barrier-on-Chip : A Technology for Reproducible Practice in Drug Testing. *Pharmaceutics* **14**, (2022).
112. Wang, J. *et al.* A virus-induced kidney disease model based on organ-on-a-chip : Pathogenesis exploration of virus-related renal dysfunctions. *Biomaterials* **219**, 119367 (2019).
113. Henry, O. Y. F. *et al.* Organs-on-chips with integrated electrodes for trans-epithelial electrical resistance (TEER) measurements of human epithelial barrier function†. *Lab Chip* **17**, 2264–2271 (2017).
114. Girija, B. G., Sailaja, R. R. N. & Madras, G. Thermal degradation and mechanical properties of PET blends. *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* **90**, 147–153 (2005).
115. Sontheimer-Phelps, A. *et al.* Human Colon-on-a-Chip Enables Continuous In Vitro Analysis of Colon Mucus Layer Accumulation and Physiology. *Cmgh* **9**, 507–526 (2020).
116. Grassart, A. *et al.* Bioengineered Human Organ-on-Chip Reveals Intestinal Microenvironment and Mechanical Forces Impacting Shigella Infection. *Cell Host Microbe* **26**, 435–444.e4 (2019).
117. Murphy, T. M., Freeman, B. D. & Paul, D. R. Physical aging of polystyrene films tracked by gas permeability. *Polymer (Guildf)*. **54**, 873–880 (2013).
118. Kim, H. J., Li, H., Collins, J. J. & Ingber, D. E. Contributions of microbiome and mechanical deformation to intestinal bacterial overgrowth and inflammation in a human gut-on-a-chip. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **113**, E7–E15 (2016).
119. Shin, W. & Kim, H. J. Intestinal barrier dysfunction orchestrates the onset of inflammatory host-microbiome cross-talk in a human gut inflammation-on-a-chip. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **115**, E10539–E10547 (2018).
120. Kasendra, M. *et al.* Development of a primary human Small Intestine-on-a-Chip using biopsy-derived organoids. *Sci. Rep.* **8**, 1–14 (2018).
121. Villenave, R. *et al.* Human gut-on-a-chip supports polarized infection of coxsackie B1 virus in vitro. *PLoS One* **12**, 1–17 (2017).

122. Shin, W. *et al.* A robust longitudinal co-culture of obligate anaerobic gut microbiome with human intestinal epithelium in an anoxic-oxic interface-on-a-chip. *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* **7**, 1–13 (2019).
123. Kim, H. J., Huh, D., Hamilton, G. & Ingber, D. E. Human gut-on-a-chip inhabited by microbial flora that experiences intestinal peristalsis-like motions and flow. *Lab Chip* **12**, 2165–2174 (2012).
124. Izdihar, K. *et al.* Structural, Mechanical, and Dielectric Properties of Polydimethylsiloxane and Silicone Elastomer for the Fabrication of Clinical-Grade Kidney Phantom. *Appl. Sci.* **11**, (2021).
125. Kim, M., Moon, B. & Hidrovo, C. Enhancement of the thermo-mechanical properties of PDMS molds for the hot embossing of PMMA. *Micromechanics and Microengineering* **23**, (2013).
126. Miranda, I., Souza, A., Sousa, P., Castanheira, E. M. S. & Lima, R. Properties and Applications of PDMS for Biomedical Engineering: A Review. (2022).
127. Tan, X. & Rodrigue, D. A Review on Porous Polymeric Membrane Preparation. Part II: Production Techniques with Polyethylene, Polydimethylsiloxane, Polypropylene. *Polymers (Basel)*. **11**, (2019).
128. Shahriar, M., Liu, J., Xu, H., Zhang, Z. & XU, C. Effects of Corona Treatment on Cellular Attachment and Morphology on Polydimethylsiloxane Micropillar Substrates. *J. Miner. Met. Mater. Soc.* **74**, 3408–3418 (2022).
129. Halldorsson, S., Lucumi, E., Gómez-sjöberg, R. & Fleming, R. M. T. Biosensors and Bioelectronics Advantages and challenges of microfluidic cell culture in polydimethylsiloxane devices. *Biosens. Bioelectron.* **63**, 218–231 (2015).
130. Bhatia, S. N. & Ingber, D. E. Microfluidic organs-on-chips. *Nat. Biotechnol.* **32**, 760–772 (2014).
131. Radisic, M. & Loskill, P. Beyond PDMS and Membranes: New Materials for Organ-on-a-Chip Devices. *ACS Appl. Polym. Mater.* **7**, 2861–2863 (2021).
132. Budhwani, K. I., Thomas, V. & Sethu, P. Lab-on-a-brane: nanofibrous polymer membranes to recreate organ–capillary interfaces. *J. Micromechanics Microengineering* **26**, 035013 (2016).
133. Baptista, D. *et al.* 3D alveolar in vitro model based on epithelialized biomimetically curved culture membranes. *Biomaterials* **266**, (2021).
134. Chuchuy, J. *et al.* Integration of electrospun membranes into low-absorption thermoplastic organ-on-chip. *ACS Biomater. Sci. Eng.* **7**, 3006–3017 (2021).
135. Pensabene, V. *et al.* Ultrathin Polymer Membranes with Patterned, Micrometric Pores for Organs-on-Chips. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **8**, 22629–22636 (2016).
136. Mitxelena-Iribarren, O., Olaizola, C., Arana, S. & Mujika, M. Versatile membrane-based microfluidic platform for in vitro drug diffusion testing mimicking in vivo environments. *Nanomedicine Nanotechnology, Biol. Med.* **39**, 102462 (2022).
137. Youn, J. *et al.* Thin and stretchable extracellular matrix (ECM) membrane reinforced by nanofiber scaffolds for developing in vitro barrier models. *Biofabrication* **14**, 25010 (2022).
138. Kanabekova, P., Dauletkanov, B., Kadyrova, A., Akhmetova, A. & Kulsharova, G. Development of a microfluidic device and nanofiber membranes for emulating air-blood barrier in lung-on-a-chip devices. in *2022 IEEE 17th International Conference on Nano/Micro Engineered and Molecular Systems (NEMS)* 124–128 (2022).
139. Sgarminato, V. *et al.* PDAC-on-chip for in vitro modeling of stromal and pancreatic cancer cell crosstalk. *Biomater. Sci.* **11**, 208–224 (2023).
140. Man, K. *et al.* Biomimetic human lung alveolar interstitium chip with extended longevity. *Kun Man. bioRxiv* 1–31 (2022).
141. Das, P. *et al.* Tunable Microstructured Membranes in Organs-on-Chips to Monitor Transendothelial Hydraulic Resistance. *Tissue Eng. - Part A* **25**, 1635–1645 (2019).
142. Pensabene, V. *et al.* Ultrathin Polymer Membranes with Patterned, Micrometric Pores for Organs-on-chips. *ACS* **8**, 22629–22636 (2016).
143. Narayanan, G., Shen, J., Boy, R., Gupta, B. S. & Tonelli, A. E. Aliphatic Polyester Nanofibers Functionalized with Cyclodextrins and Cyclodextrin-Guest Inclusion Complexes. *Polymers (Basel)*. **10**, 1–26 (2018).
144. Arik, Y. B. *et al.* Collagen I Based Enzymatically Degradable Membranes for Organ-on-a-Chip Barrier Models. *ACS Biomater. Sci. Eng.* **7**, 2998–3005 (2021).
145. Zamprogno, P. *et al.* Mechanical Properties of Soft Biological Membranes for Organ-on-a-Chip Assessed by Bulge Test and AFM. *ACS Biomater. Sci. Eng.* **7**, 2990–2997 (2021).
146. Frenkel, N. *et al.* Long-Lived Human Lymphatic Endothelial Cells to Study Lymphatic Biology and Lymphatic Vessel/Tumor Coculture in a 3D Microfluidic Model. *ACS Biomater. Sci. Eng.* **7**, 3030–3042 (2021).
147. Tasiopoulos, C. P., Gustafsson, L., Wijngaart, W. Van Der & Hedhammar, M. Fibrillar Nanomembranes of Recombinant Spider Silk Protein Support Cell Co-culture in an In Vitro Blood Vessel Wall Model. *ACS Biomater. Sci. Eng.* **7**, 3332–3339 (2021).
148. Kang, T. H. & Kim, H. J. Farewell to animal testing: Innovations on human intestinal microphysiological systems. *Micromachines* **7**, (2016).
149. Fedi, A. *et al.* In vitro models replicating the human intestinal epithelium for absorption and metabolism studies: A systematic review. *J. Control. Release* **335**, 247–268 (2021).
150. Tavakol, D. N., Fleischer, S. & Vunjak-novakovic, G. Harnessing organs-on-a-chip to model tissue regeneration. *Cell Stem Cell* **28**, 993–1015 (2021).
151. Vunjak-novakovic, G., Ronaldson-bouchard, K. & Radisic, M. Organs-on-a-chip models for biological research. *Cell* **184**, 4597–4611 (2021).
152. Ronaldson-bouchard, K. *et al.* A multi-organ chip with matured tissue niches linked by vascular flow. *Nat. Biomed. Eng.* **6**, 351–371 (2022).
153. Nolan, H., Wang, D. & Zwischenberger, J. B. Artificial lung basics: Fundamental challenges, alternative designs and future innovations. *Organogenesis* **7**, 23–27 (2011).
154. Nguyen, B. T. D., Nguyen Thi, H. Y., Nguyen Thi, B. P., Kang, D.-K. & Kim, J. F. The Roles of Membrane Technology in Artificial Organs: Current Challenges and Perspectives. *Membranes (Basel)*. **11**, 1–33 (2021).
155. Supady, A. *et al.* Outcome Prediction in Patients with Severe COVID-19 Requiring Extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation — A Retrospective International Multicenter Study. *Membranes (Basel)*. **11**, (2021).
156. Punjabi, P. P. & Taylor, K. M. The science and practice of cardiopulmonary bypass: From cross circulation to ECMO and SIRS. *Glob. Cardiol. Sci. Pract.* **32**, (2013).
157. Rehder, K. J. *et al.* Active Rehabilitation During Extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation as a Bridge to Lung Transplantation. *Respir. Care* **58**, 1291–1298 (2013).

158. Dabaghi, M. *et al.* An ultra-thin, all PDMS-based microfluidic lung assist device with high oxygenation capacity. *Biomicrofluidics* **13**, 1–9 (2019).
159. Murphy, D. A. *et al.* Extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation — Hemostatic Complications. *Transfus. Med. Rev.* **29**, 90–101 (2015).
160. Thangappan, K., Cavarocchi, N. C., Baram, M., Toma, B. & Hirose, H. Systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS) after extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO): Incidence, risks and survivals. *Dep. Surg. Fac. Pap.* **Paper 144**, (2016).
161. Dabaghi, M. *et al.* Miniaturization of Artificial Lungs toward Portability. *Adv. Mater. Technol.* 1–18 (2020)
162. Potkay, J. A. The promise of microfluidic artificial lungs. *Lab Chip* **14**, 4122–4138 (2014).
163. Astor, T. L. & Borenstein, J. T. The microfluidic artificial lung : Mimicking nature ' s blood path design to solve the biocompatibility paradox. *Artif. Organs* **46**, 1227–1239 (2022).
164. Munshi, L. *et al.* Intensive Care Physiotherapy during Extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation for Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome. *Ann. Am. Thorac. Soc.* **14**, 246–253 (2017).
165. Conrad, S. A. & Rycus, P. T. Extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation in Critical Care: Past , Present , and Future. *J. Card. Crit. Care* **1**, 60–64 (2017).
166. Federspiel, W. J. & Henchir, K. A. Lung , Artificial : Basic Principles and Current Applications. *Encycl. Biomater. Biomed. Eng.* 910–921 (2004)
167. Stamatialis, D. *Biomedical membranes and (bio) artificial organs*. vol. 2 (World Scientific, 2017).
168. Nagase, K., Kohori, F. & Sakai, K. Oxygen transfer performance of a membrane oxygenator composed of crossed and parallel hollow fibers. *Biochem. Eng. J.* **24**, 105–113 (2005).
169. Hoganson, D. M. *et al.* Branched vascular network architecture: A new approach to lung assist device technology. *J. Thorac. Cardiovasc. Surg.* **140**, 990–995 (2010).
170. McCaughan, J. S., Weeder, R., Schuder, J. C. & Blakemore, W. S. Evaluation of new nonwetable macroporous membranes with high permeability coefficients for possible use on a membrane oxygenator. *J. Thorac. Cardiovasc. Surg.* **40**, 574–581 (1960).
171. Evseev, A. K., Zhuravel, S. V., Alentiev, A. Y., Goroncharovskaya, I. V. & Petrikov, S. S. Membranes in Extracorporeal Blood Oxygenation Technology. *Membr. Membr. Technol.* **1**, 201–211 (2019).
172. Horton, S. *et al.* Experience with the Jostra Rotaflow and QuadroxD oxygenator for ECMO. *Perfusion* **19**, 17–23 (2004).
173. Peek, G. J., Killer, H. M., Reeves, R., Sosnowski, A. W. & Firmin, R. K. Early Experience with a Polymethyl Pentene Oxygenator for Adult Extracorporeal Life Support. *ASAIO J.* **48**, 480–482 (2002).
174. Kammermeyer, K. Silicone Rubber as a Selective Barrier Gas. *Ind. Eng. Chem.* **49**, 1685–1686 (1957).
175. Kolobow, T. & Bowman, R. L. Construction and evaluation of an alveolar membrane artificial heart-lung. *Trans. Am. Soc. Artif. Intern. Organs* **9**, 238–243 (1963).
176. Bramson, M. L. *et al.* A New Disposable membrane oxygenator with integral heat exchange. *J. Thorac. Cardiovasc. Surg.* **50**, 391–400 (1965).
177. Landé, A. J. *et al.* Clinical experience with a membrane pump-oxygenator. *Ann. Thorac. Surg.* **10**, 409–423 (1970).
178. Kolobow, T., Spragg, R. G., Pierce, J. E. & Zapol, W. M. Extended term (to 16 days) partial extracorporeal blood gas exchange with the spiral membrane lung in unanesthetized lambs. *Trans. Am. Soc. Artif. Intern. Organs* **17**, 350–354 (1971).
179. Merkel, T. C., Bondar, V. I., Nagai, K., Freeman, B. D. & Pinnau, I. Gas Sorption, Diffusion, and Permeation in Poly(dimethylsiloxane). *J. Polym. Sci. Part B Polym. Phys.* **38**, 415–434 (2000).
180. Lamberti, A., Marasso, S. L. & Cocuzza, M. PDMS membranes with tunable gas permeability for microfluidic applications. *RSC Adv.* **4**, 61415–61419 (2014).
181. Berean, K. *et al.* The effect of crosslinking temperature on the permeability of PDMS membranes : Evidence of extraordinary CO 2 and CH 4 gas permeation. *Sep. Purif. Technol.* **122**, 96–104 (2014).
182. Markov, D. A., Lillie, E. M., Garbett, S. P. & Mccawley, L. J. Variation in diffusion of gases through PDMS due to plasma surface treatment and storage conditions. *Biomed. Microdevices* **16**, 91–96 (2014).
183. Houston, K. S., Weinkauff, D. H. & Stewart, F. F. Gas transport characteristics of plasma treated poly (dimethylsiloxane) and polyphosphazene membrane materials. *J. Memb. Sci.* **205**, 103–112 (2002).
184. Matharoo, H. *et al.* Steel reinforced composite silicone membranes and its integration to microfluidic oxygenators for high performance gas exchange. *Biomicrofluidics* **12**, (2018).
185. Dabaghi, M. *et al.* An artificial placenta type microfluidic blood oxygenator with double-sided gas transfer microchannels and its integration as a neonatal lung assist device. *Biomicrofluidics* **12**, 1–17 (2018).
186. Zhang, X., Du, B., Dai, Y., Zheng, W. & Ruan, X. Hemocompatible polydimethylsiloxane / polysulfone ultrathin composite membrane for extracorporeal membrane oxygenation. *Sep. Purif. Technol.* **302**, 122028 (2022).
187. Dharia, A. *et al.* Silicon Micropore based Parallel Plate Membrane Oxygenator. *Artif. Organs* **42**, 166–173 (2018).
188. Abada, E. N., Feinberg, B. & Roy, S. Evaluation of silicon membranes for extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO). *Biomed. Microdevices* **20**, (2018).
189. Chang, Y., Chang, W., Shih, Y., Wei, T. & Hsiue, G. Zwitterionic Sulfobetaine-Grafted Poly (vinylidene fluoride) Membrane with Highly Effective Blood Compatibility via Atmospheric Plasma-Induced Surface Copolymerization. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **3**, 1228–1237 (2011).
190. Yi, E. *et al.* Superamphiphobic blood-repellent surface modification of porous fluoropolymer membranes for blood oxygenation applications. *J. Memb. Sci.* **648**, 120363 (2022).
191. Park, A. *et al.* Blood Oxygenation Using Fluoropolymer-Based Artificial Lung Membranes. *ACS Biomater. Sci. Eng.* **6**, 6424–6434 (2020).
192. Wu, W. I. *et al.* Lung assist device: Development of microfluidic oxygenators for preterm infants with respiratory failure. *Lab Chip* **13**, 2641–2650 (2013).
193. Rochow, N. *et al.* An integrated array of microfluidic oxygenators as a neonatal lung assist device: In vitro characterization and in vivo demonstration. *Artif. Organs* **38**, 856–866 (2014).

194. Rieper, T., Müller, C. & Reinecke, H. Novel scalable and monolithically integrated extracorporeal gas exchange device. *Biomed. Microdevices* **17**, 1–10 (2015).
195. Gimbel, A. A., Flores, E., Koo, A., García-Cardeña, G. & Borenstein, J. T. Development of a biomimetic microfluidic oxygen transfer device. *Lab Chip* **16**, 3227–3234 (2016).
196. Thompson, A. J., Marks, L. H., Goudie, M. J., Handa, H. & Potkay, J. A. A small-scale, rolled-membrane microfluidic artificial lung designed towards future large area manufacturing. *Biomicrofluidics* **11**, 024113-1-024113-12 (2017).
197. Dabaghi, M. *et al.* An ultra-thin highly flexible microfluidic device for blood oxygenation. *Lab Chip* **18**, 3780–3789 (2018).
198. Thompson, A. J., Ma, L. J., Plegue, T. J. & Potkay, J. A. Design Analysis and Optimization of a Single-Layer PDMS Microfluidic Artificial Lung. *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.* **66**, 1082–1093 (2019).
199. Malankowska, M. *et al.* Understanding blood oxygenation in a microfluidic meander double side membrane contactor. *Sensors Actuators, B Chem.* **288**, 414–424 (2019).
200. Dabaghi, M. *et al.* A Pumpless Microfluidic Neonatal Lung Assist Device for Support of Preterm Neonates in Respiratory Distress. *Adv. Sci.* **7**, 1–16 (2020).
201. Dabaghi, M. *et al.* Microfluidic blood oxygenators with integrated hollow chambers for enhanced air exchange from all four sides. *J. Memb. Sci.* **596**, (2020).
202. Lachaux, J. *et al.* A compact integrated microfluidic oxygenator with high gas exchange efficiency and compatibility for long-lasting endothelialization. *Lab Chip* (2021).
203. Hung, T. K., Borovetz, H. S. & Weissman, M. H. Transport and flow phenomena in a microchannel membrane oxygenator. *Ann. Biomed. Eng.* **5**, 343–361 (1977).
204. Lee, J. K., Kung, M. C. & Mockros, L. F. Microchannel Technologies for Artificial Lungs: (3) Open Rectangular Channels. *ASAIO J.* **54**, 390–395 (2008).
205. Potkay, J. A., Magnetta, M., Vinson, A. & Cmolik, B. Bio-inspired, efficient, artificial lung employing air as the ventilating gas. *Lab Chip* **11**, 2901–2909 (2011).
206. Hoganson, D. M., Pryor, H. I., Bassett, E. K., Spool, I. D. & Vacanti, J. P. Lung assist device technology with physiologic blood flow developed on a tissue engineered scaffold platform. *Lab Chip* **11**, 700–707 (2011).
207. Kniazeva, T., Hsiao, J. C., Charest, J. L. & Borenstein, J. T. A microfluidic respiratory assist device with high gas permeance for artificial lung applications. *Biomed. Microdevices* **13**, 315–323 (2011).
208. Kniazeva, T. *et al.* Performance and scaling effects in a multilayer microfluidic extracorporeal lung oxygenation device. *Lab Chip* **12**, 1686–1695 (2012).
209. Lee, J. K., Kung, H. H. & Mockros, L. F. Microchannel technologies for artificial lungs: (1) theory. *ASAIO J.* **54**, 372–382 (2008).
210. Kung, M. C., Lee, J. K., Kung, H. H. & Mockros, L. F. Microchannel Technologies for Artificial Lungs: (2) Screen-filled Wide Rectangular Channels. *ASAIO J.* **54**, 383–389 (2008).
211. Murray, C. D. The physiological principle of minimum work applied to the angle of branching of arteries. *J. Gen. Physiol.* **9**, 835–841 (1926).
212. Burgess, K. A., Hu, H. H., Wagner, W. R. & Federspiel, W. J. Towards microfabricated biohybrid artificial lung modules for chronic respiratory support. *Biomed. Microdevices* **11**, 117–127 (2009).
213. Malankowska, M. *et al.* On the Improvement of Alveolar-Like Microfluidic Devices for Efficient Blood Oxygenation. *Adv. Mater. Technol.* **6**, 1–44 (2021).
214. Femmer, T., Eggersdorfer, M. L., Kuehne, A. J. C. & Wessling, M. Efficient gas-liquid contact using microfluidic membrane devices with staggered herringbone mixers. *Lab Chip* **15**, 3132–3137 (2015).
215. Santos, J. *et al.* Toward development of a higher flow rate hemocompatible biomimetic microfluidic blood oxygenator. *Micromachines* **12**, (2021).
216. Vedula, E. M. *et al.* Multilayer Scaling of a Biomimetic Microfluidic Oxygenator. *ASAIO J.* **68**, 1312–1319 (2022).
217. Wu, W.-I. *et al.* Lung Assist Device: Development of Microfluidic Oxygenators for Preterm Infants with Respiratory Failure 5. (2013).
218. Isenberg, B. C. *et al.* A Clinical-Scale Microfluidic Respiratory Assist Device with 3D Branching Vascular Networks. *Adv. Sci.* **2207455**, 1–13 (2023).
219. Canic, S. *et al.* Modeling viscoelastic behavior of arterial walls and their interaction with pulsatile blood flow. *J. Appl. Math.* **67**, 164–193 (2006).
220. Kefalides, N. A. & Borel, J. P. Morphology and Ultrastructure of Basement Membranes. in *Current Topics in Membranes* vol. 56 19–42 (Elsevier, 2005).
221. VanDersarl, J. J., Xu, A. M. & Melosh, N. A. Rapid spatial and temporal controlled signal delivery over large cell culture areas. *Lab Chip* **11**, 3057–3063 (2011).
222. Chung, H. H. *et al.* Highly permeable silicon membranes for shear free chemotaxis and rapid cell labeling†. *Lab Chip* **14**, 2456–2468 (2014).
223. Jain, P. *et al.* Reconstruction of Ultra-thin Alveolar-capillary Basement Membrane Mimics. *Adv. Biol.* **5**, 2000427 (2021).
224. Liliensiek, S. J. *et al.* Characterization of Endothelial Basement Membrane Nanotopography in Rhesus Macaque as a Guide for Vessel Tissue Engineering. *Tissue Eng. - Part A* **15**, 2643–2651 (2009).
225. Kojic, S. P., Stojanovic, G. M. & Radonic, V. Novel Cost-Effective Microfluidic Chip Based on Hybrid Fabrication and Its Comprehensive Characterization. (2019).
226. Feaugas, T. *et al.* Design of artificial vascular devices: Hemodynamic evaluation of shear-induced thrombogenicity. *Front. Mech. Eng.* **9**, (2023).
227. Newman, G. *et al.* Challenge of material haemocompatibility for microfluidic blood-contacting applications. *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* **11**, (2023).
228. Kojic, S. Design, Fabrication and Testing of Microfluidic Chips for Biomedical Applications. (2021).
229. Wang, L. *et al.* Gut-on-a-chip for exploring the transport mechanism of Hg(II). *Microsystems Nanoeng.* **9**, (2023).
230. Shin, Y. C. *et al.* Three-Dimensional Regeneration of Patient-Derived Intestinal Organoid Epithelium in a Physiodynamic Mucosal Interface-on-a-Chip. *Micromachines* **11**, (2020).
231. Jeon, M. S. *et al.* Contributions of the microbiome to intestinal inflammation in a gut-on-a-chip. *Nano Conver.* **9**, (2022).

